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D3.7 – User Community Support and Engagement Report (final)

WP3: Community, Support and Use Cases

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Executive Summary

This document is a final update to deliverables [D3.4 - User Community Support and Engagement Report \(halftime update\)](#) (PM18) and [D3.5 - Best Practice Guides](#) (PM24). It describes BioExcel's community support and engagement activities from PM19 (July 2020) up until and including PM42 (June 2022). It includes a summary for this period of the community events BioExcel (co-)organised or participated in, the in-depth support we have offered to users, our work on standards and best practice, including updates to our Best Practice Guides, and how we have analysed user & community needs to drive our activities.

During this reporting period BioExcel has:

- (Co-)organised and/or participated in **136 community events, attended by around 10 000 community members**, at which we shared scientific results from the BioExcel Use Cases and/or the capabilities of BioExcel software, at external workshops and conferences and at training courses run together with PRACE, the EuroHPC National Competence Centres, and other HPC CoEs. We organised a workshop - [“Best Practices in QM/MM Simulation of Biomolecular Systems”](#), which was **attended by around 1000 people**. Through our support and engagement work we have started seeing increased uptake of the new GROMACS-CP2K interface we developed, and we deem to have successfully **seeded a new user community**.
- Hosted **23 [BioExcel Webinars](#), attended live by over 1700 people**.
- Seen our [YouTube channel](#) gain significant momentum, with **~4x greater content consumption rate and ~3x faster growth in subscribers** than during the previous reporting period.
- Provided direct **in-depth support to over 1900 community members**, including by **answering around 1500 questions on the AskBioExcel and GROMACS forums combined**.
- Created, improved, and made available **16 tutorials** for users of BioExcel core software.
- Engaged in existing and new **pilot projects with industry** and pursued our planned strategy regarding what BioExcel will deliver for industrial users, namely:
 - Prepare and establish BioExcel Enterprises
 - Consolidate existing and establish new business opportunities
 - Further define and validate the BioExcel value proposition
- Supported the [National Centre for Supercomputing Applications in Bulgaria](#), which hosts the [EuroHPC Discoverer system](#) by providing

lectures and hands-on training in BioExcel software functionality, methodologies and performance on two separate courses.

- Continued to participate in community **development of standards** such as the Common Workflow Language, FAIR computational workflows, FAIR Digital Objects, BioCompute Objects and Research Object Crate
- Expanded the **Best Practice Guides** (BPGs) first published at PM24 as part of deliverable [D3.5 - Best Practice Guides](#) as we described and planned in that deliverable. We have:
 - Updated the CP2K biomolecular QM/MM BPG to include [usage of GROMACS together with CP2K for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems](#)
 - Captured the outcomes of our workshop on [Best Practices in QM/MM Simulation of Biomolecular Systems](#) in a [new software-agnostic Best Practice Guide on general QM/MM modelling & simulation methodology](#).
 - Added guidance to the [GROMACS BPG](#) detailing how to obtain good **performance on two additional European HPC systems** - JUWELS BOOSTER (PRACE) and Discoverer (EuroHPC) - and on using GROMACS postprocessing tools.
- Adapted activities on an ongoing basis, including after **gathering input, including feedback, from over 1700 community members** and analysing user needs.
- **Interviewed 8 Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs)** in a range of biomolecular modelling & simulation research areas to help us assess what we have achieved in BioExcel-2 and, crucially, to help us look ahead and calibrate our vision towards the **exascale future**.
- Designed and begun to prototype an **Ambassador programme** in order to strengthen links with local computational biomolecular research communities **across the EU**, starting with **EU13 member states**.

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Introduction

This document describes work carried out by BioExcel Centre of Excellence supporting and engaging with our user communities during the period PM18 (July 2020) to PM42 (June 2022). It includes reports on community events we (co-)organised and participated in, updates to our Best Practice Guides, and work done to help ensure that all BioExcel activities are driven by the needs of the community.

The BioExcel User Communities

In [D3.4 - User Community Support and Engagement Report \(halftime update\)](#) we set out the BioExcel user communities and reported activities addressing each community. These are shown in **Table 1** as a reminder, as we again use them in this document to structure the report on our activities during PM19-PM42.

User community	BioExcel software
Integrative modelling	HADDOCK
Classical molecular modelling and simulation	GROMACS, PMX
Hybrid QM/MM molecular modelling and simulation	GROMACS, CP2K
Workflow tools & standards	BioBB, CWL
Industry	All

Table 1: *The BioExcel user communities*

The BioExcel user communities are overlapping and mutually non-exclusive in the sense that any individual researcher may belong to multiple user communities. However, they are a partitioning that reflects the core software applications we develop and the computational modelling & simulation methodology or approach that each embodies. The BioExcel user communities also align naturally with many of our support and training activities and promotion of best practices and standards. The “Industry” community is an exception, as it includes use of any of the codes and methodologies covered in the other user communities but with a specific focus on engaging with and supporting researchers in industry.

Many events we (co-)organise or participate in also align with one particular BioExcel user community, especially if they focus on one particular software application or methodology. But many events, especially conferences and workshops focusing on a particular research question rather than on methodology, span multiple user communities. This reflects the fact that tackling any particular research question often involves combining a number of techniques

and software applications, as is exemplified by some of the BioExcel Use Case work reported in [D3.6 - Pre-exascale showcase calculation and Use Case final report](#).

Overview of Community Support and Engagement Activities

Here we present a high-level overview and a few noteworthy highlights for the reporting period of our community participation and in-depth support activities, our promotion of best practices and standards, and our analysis of user community feedback and needs. Details regarding these activities pertaining to each of the BioExcel user communities are given in the community-specific sections in the rest of this document.

Community Participation

BioExcel (co-)organised and/or participated in 136 community events, attended by around 10 000 community members. We presented scientific results that emerged from our demonstrator Use Case research work, which is described in detail in deliverable [D3.6 - Pre-exascale Showcase Calculations and Use Case Final Report](#), and we shared advances in our core software and workflow tools with the community. In many cases the results presented were enabled by new functionality or improved performance that we developed, hence making the community of current or potential future users of the software aware of these capabilities paved the way for their wider productive use and impactful exploitation of HPC resources.

Many of the events we organised - independently or together with other bodies such as PRACE, the EuroHPC National Competence Centres, other HPC CoEs, etc. - were already reported from the perspective of training and dissemination in deliverable [D4.4 – Final report on dissemination and training](#). That deliverable also reported in significant detail on our flagship BioExcel conference event, the [EMBO workshop “Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulation”](#). In this current deliverable we further detail which events, or which aspects of which events, were relevant to each specific user community and what our participation contributed.

In addition to continuing to strengthen and grow the user communities of core BioExcel software, we set out in BioExcel-2 to support and grow a new BioExcel user community around hybrid QM/MM modelling and simulation using CP2K through GROMACS with our newly developed interface. On this front we shared experiences from our Use Case and development work. We also provided ample training to researchers in concrete usage of CP2K’s QM/MM functionality, both as a standalone application and in combination with GROMACS. We organised a software-agnostic community workshop - [“Best Practices in QM/MM Simulation of Biomolecular Systems”](#) - centred on methodological issues and best practices we believed were critical to make this user community aware of in order to enable them to be scientifically productive. This workshop was attended by just under 1000 people, and recordings of the event accrued around 8800 YouTube views. We captured the workshop outcomes in a [Best Practice Guide on QM/MM](#)

[Simulation of Biomolecular Systems](#), which we believe will remain a valuable reference far beyond the lifetime of BioExcel-2. Thanks to these efforts and efforts providing in-depth support, tutorials, etc. we have started seeing increased uptake of the GROMACS-CP2K interface and what we deem to be the successful seeding of a new user community.

We hosted 23 webinars as part of our [BioExcel Webinar series](#), and these were attended live by over 1700 people. Over the same period, recordings of all BioExcel Webinars on our YouTube channel regardless of when during BioExcel-2 they were published accrued over 27 000 views. As well as featuring BioExcel core software - GROMACS, PMX, HADDOCK, CP2K, BioBB - and results from the BioExcel Use Cases, the webinar series provided a platform for a wide range of topics of interest to the community, including other important biomolecular modelling and simulation software.

Comparing analytics of the [BioExcel YouTube channel](#) during PM19-PM42 with that during PM1-PM18 shows that it gained significant momentum over the course of BioExcel-2. The number of daily views, the daily cumulative time watched, and the number of subscribers all increased following a similar trend - see **Figure 1** for the number of daily views as an example, and **Table 2** for an overview of channel analytics quantifying this growth. Metrics show ~4x greater content consumption rate and ~3x faster growth in subscribers during the second BioExcel-2 period compared to the first. At PM42 total views of all content hosted on our channel was 103 000, total watched time was 9100 hours, and total subscribers 2600.

Figure 1: Number of daily views across all content on the BioExcel YouTube channel from PM1 (January 2019) until PM42 (June 2022).

	Period 1 PM1 - PM18	Period 2 PM19 - PM42	Ratio (Period2 / Period1)
Views per month	777	3250	4.2
Watch time per month (hours)	72	280	3.9
Subscribers gained per month	28	79	2.8

Table 2: BioExcel YouTube channel analytics showing around 4x greater content consumption rate and ~3x faster growth in subscribers during the second BioExcel-2 period compared to the first. At PM42 total views of all content on the channel was 103 000, total watched time 9100 hours, and total subscribers 2600.

In-depth Support

BioExcel continued to provide in-depth support for the project's core applications and their usage. We ran the [AskBioExcel forum](#) and, following our successful transition away from the longstanding GROMACS mailing list, the [GROMACS forum](#), and answered users' queries and kept users up to date with developments. BioExcel staff also supported users directly at Q&A sessions at dedicated events, through direct discussion (mostly virtual meetings due to the pandemic), and by email. During this period over 1900 community members were provided with direct in-depth by BioExcel in their usage of core applications through these mechanisms, with around 1500 questions answered on AskBioExcel and GROMACS forums.

BioExcel also created, improved, and provided tutorials relating to BioExcel software and workflows, and 16 tutorials were made available to users. These may be used for training through guided practicals or by means of self study, and surveys in fact confirm that users consider these to be a highly valuable and desirable primary form of support material. Details of these tutorials are described in each user community section.

In deliverable [D3.4 - User Community Support and Engagement Report \(halftime update\)](#) we described a 2+ year strategy regarding what BioExcel will deliver for industrial users. This strategy prioritised the following three key elements: (1) Prepare and establish BioExcel Enterprises, (2) consolidate existing and establish new business opportunities, and (3) further define and validate the BioExcel value proposition. During PM19-PM42 we continued existing pilot projects with industry and initiated new ones, offering support, consultancy, training, etc. in BioExcel software to a number of industrial partners. This fulfilled a valuable role, enabling us to learn lessons on how best to engage with potential commercial customers in future to initiate paid-for work, e.g. through BioExcel Enterprises. Details on how we have delivered on these three points, the pilot projects, and our engagement with industry generally is described in the industry community section in this document.

As part of our effort to expand the communities we support, BioExcel engaged with the [National Centre for Supercomputing Applications in Bulgaria](#), which hosts the [EuroHPC Discoverer system](#) (see also the [Press Release regarding Discoverer's Inauguration](#)). We supported new users by providing lectures and hands-on training in BioExcel software and methodologies (docking, free energy calculations) in the [PRACE 2021 Autumn School "Fundamentals of Biomolecular Simulation and Virtual Drug Development"](#), which was attended by 165 researchers, and we [hosted the recordings](#) of this event on our channel to facilitate access by that user community. We were also granted pre-production access to Discoverer in order to assist with ensuring optimal versions of GROMACS and

CP2K were installed, and we provided practical sessions in these applications as part of another [PRACE course: HPC Fundamentals for end-users](#), which was attended by 58 researchers.

Standards and Best Practice

BioExcel has continued to participate in community development of standards such as the Common Workflow Language, FAIR computational workflows, Digital Research Objects, and others during the period PM19-PM42 (see also subsection on [standards for computational workflows](#) below).

BioExcel have been instrumental in establishing the [RO-Crate community](#), co-chairing bi-weekly community meetings and developing the specifications. Here we are building a standard for FAIR packaging research data described using structured metadata, which have now expanded into multiple domains and communities [<https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053>] and been cited by EOSC Interoperability Framework [<https://doi.org/10.2777/620649>] as a recent implementation of [Research Objects](#) (RO), which was initially established by UNIMAN before and during BioExcel-1.

We have also been involved in the [FAIR Digital Object](#) (FDO) forum, which are now preparing a series of formal recommendations, of which implementation with RO-Crate is mentioned in a recent whitepaper [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5872645>]. One working group of FDO is focused on developing a *Canonical Workflow Framework for Research* ([CWFR](#)), and in a recent [Data Intelligence special issue](#), RO-Crate and RO is cited in 7 of the articles, including our article on BioExcel's BioBB as canonical workflow building blocks [<https://doi.org/10.1162/dint a 00135>].

The notion of FAIR Digital Objects have gained traction within the European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)), and as this will impact many projects and researchers we are contributing with our existing knowledge from Research Objects and workflows.

We have contributed to improve FAIR metrics measures as part of the “Apples-to-Apples FAIR hackathon”, developing a benchmark to test [FAIR Signposting](#). This approach has evolved from earlier with BioExcel, RO-Crate and WorkflowHub.

We have built on and expanded the Best Practice Guides (BPGs) first published at PM24 as part of deliverable [D3.5 - Best Practice Guides](#), as described as planned in that deliverable. This includes updates regarding [usage of GROMACS together with CP2K for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems](#), and a [new software-agnostic Best Practice Guide on QM/MM modelling & simulation methodology](#) that captures the outcomes [our workshop on the topic](#). We have added guidance to the [GROMACS BPG](#) on how to obtain good performance on two additional European HPC systems - JUWELS BOOSTER (PRACE) and Discoverer (EuroHPC) - and on using GROMACS postprocessing tools. These and other BPG updates are described in more detail in each user community section.

We have published the *Ten Simple Rules for making a software tool workflow-ready* [<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009823>]. As mentioned in deliverable D2.6 – *Integration of BioExcel software framework with standards and international initiatives* [doi:[10.5281/zenodo.5824544](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5824544)], WP2 is also developing a whitepaper to document HPC on CWL.

User & Community Needs Analysis and Feedback

We have continued to engage with our user communities to identify their needs and use these insights to guide our activities, from prioritising development goals for BioExcel software, to designing the community events we organise, the content and method of delivery of training, and our support mechanisms. Our community participation and provision of in-depth support means we are constantly in contact with users and noticing issues and unmet needs that come up most frequently, as well as unexpected edge cases, and we adapt what we do in response.

In order to ensure and demonstrate that BioExcel is truly user driven, we have also developed and implemented some more formal methodologies to capture insights arising from many distinct meaningful engagements with users of BioExcel tools and services, by gaining their opinion on the tool or service provided or on broader topics. The underlying model for this process is depicted in **Figure 2**. These engagements and methodologies take many forms, including online surveys (e.g. using Google Forms), Q&A sessions, discussions, in-depth interviews, discussion groups or focus groups, polls or surveys during webinars, post-training-event feedback forms, questionnaires, informal in-person interactions at events, etc. Findings from these have been fed back to the wider project, including both the technical work packages (WP1/WP2), training (WP4), and the sustainability WP (WP5).

Figure 2: Generic process for engaging and gathering feedback from various users

and communities followed by resulting actions to ensure that BioExcel is user-driven.

We have gathered input, including feedback, from over 1700 community members. For each user community, we include results and analyses of any user surveys that were run and findings from any other engagements, as well as discussion of how these have guided the Centre's support and engagement activities.

We decided to interview a number of Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) in the wider field of computational biomolecular modelling & simulation in order to help us assess what we have achieved in BioExcel-2 and, crucially, to help us look ahead and calibrate our vision towards the exascale future by gathering perspectives of experts in a range of research areas whose practice represents the current state of the art. This has helped us understand whether we are missing any strategic insights and to what extent we are on a trajectory that will enable us to successfully meet the challenges and take advantage of opportunities in the exascale era, which should help us plan for a potential future continuation of the Centre. The procedure and findings of the 8 KOL interviews we conducted are discussed in the section "Key Opinion Leader (KOL) in-depth interviews".

The BioExcel Ambassador Programme

In pursuit of the goal of increasing our reach and impact serving the needs of biomolecular modelling and simulation researchers across the EU and beyond we have begun to define and prototype the BioExcel Ambassador programme as a mechanism of community engagement. Our vision is to create and strengthen links with parts of the community with which we currently don't have strong direct links, so that we may better understand their needs and provide whatever is needed to raise awareness and uptake of the BioExcel core applications. In particular we have in mind as a first priority forging stronger links with research communities in EU13 member states. In this endeavour we are mirroring the EuroHPC HPC infrastructure strategy, with which we expect to be able to align synergistically in future by supporting onboarding of new users and providing support and training in core BioExcel software and associated modelling and simulation methodologies, as we have already begun to do with the [Discoverer HPC service](#) hosted by [NCSA in Bulgaria](#).

Our aim is to appoint a BioExcel ambassador in each community (e.g. in each EU13 member state). We expect ambassadors to be affiliated with a leading (within their local context) academic institution and to be working in the field of computational biomolecular research. An ambassador should be someone who has extensive links within their local (i.e. national) community, and who can both disseminate what BioExcel can offer to their local research community as well as represent their community to us in order to help us better understand its needs. This will enable the organisation of tailored training and other community events for local users, both on national level and, by identifying common themes, on a pan-European level, making it feasible to organise events that would not otherwise

take place due to insufficient demand on a local level and without us being in a position to act as intermediary by identifying common needs and connecting various communities. In many but certainly not all cases BioExcel would organise these events ourselves and provide training or other expertise or support. BioExcel Ambassadors would be able to input into prioritisation within the development roadmaps of BioExcel Software.

We have already confirmed the interest in participation of prospective Ambassadors from Bulgaria, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Turkey.

Integrative Modelling (HADDOCK)

Community Participation

BioExcel (co-)organised and participated in a number of events in which we engaged with and/or supported over 3000 members of the community interested in integrative modelling, including both current and potential future users of HADDOCK and related software, as shown in **Table 3**.

Date	Event and participation	Participants
07/10/2020	Lecture & tutorial - "Docking with HADDOCK" at the CCPBioSim Training Week	46
20/10/2020	Lecture - "Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes" at the 2020 Virtual NMR Symposium	115
26/11/2020	Lectures - "Exploring protein docking with HADDOCK" and "Interface prediction and binding affinity prediction", and Q&A at EMBL-EBI Structural Bioinformatics course	24
30/11/2020 - 04/12/2020	Lectures - "Docking Basics", HADDOCK Tutorial, and Presentation - "When HADDOCK meets GROMACS" at the BioExcel Winter School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
02/12/2020 - 04/12/2020	Lectures - "Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes" at ThermoFisher Winter School on Integrative Structural Biology	60
15/12/2020	Webinar - "Drug repurposing against SARS-Cov-2 using HADDOCK" at Interdisciplinary consortium for the study of pandemics, CIC biomaGUNE	35
22/03/2021	Lectures - "General introduction to integrative modelling and HADDOCK", "HADDOCK Advanced Topics", "AI-based integrative modelling with LightDock", and Tutorials - "Modelling antibody-antigen complexes with HADDOCK", "Integrative modelling of membrane complexes with LightDock and HADDOCK" at WeNMR / HADDOCK Workshop colocated with International Symposium on Grids & Clouds 2021	20
04/05/2021 - 05/05/2021	Presentation - "Solving 3D puzzles by integrative modelling using PDB structures" at PDB50: A special symposium celebrating the 50th anniversary of the Protein Data Bank	300

30/05/2021 - 05/06/2021	Lectures - “Basic principles of docking and scoring”, “Information-driven docking”, “Challenges in docking”, and Practicals - “Integrative docking with HADDOCK and LightDock”, at EMBO Practical Course Integrative modelling of biomolecular interactions	24
07/06/2021 - 11/06/2021	Lectures - “Docking Basics” and HADDOCK Tutorial at the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
19/06/2021	SBGrid Consortium Webinar on HADDOCK	30
02/07/2021	Presentation - “Deep learning approaches to learn interaction patterns from protein-protein interfaces” in the 6th Deep Learning on Supercomputers Workshop at ISC High Performance 2021 HPC Conference	50
29/06/2021 - 01/07/2021	Poster presentation at International Society of Quantum Biology and Pharmacology (ISQBP) 2021 President’s Meeting	150
07/07/2021 - 11/07/2021	Lecture and practical training at EU-ASEAN HPC Virtual School 2021: System Design and HPC Applications	80
02/08/2021 - 06/08/2021	Presentation - “DeepRank: A deep learning framework for data mining 3D protein-protein interfaces” at New directions of AI in structural biology workshop at CIRM (Centre International de Rencontres Mathématiques)	50
20/09/2021 - 24/09/2021	Lectures - “Basics of docking for drug design”, “Introduction to HADDOCK” and HADDOCK demonstration and hands-on practical session at PRACE Autumn School: Fundamentals of Biomolecular Simulations and Virtual Drug Development (hosted by Bulgarian National Center for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system)	165
24/09/2021	Instruct-ERIC Software Developers Exchange Webinar - “The machinery behind the HADDOCK webservers”	25
29/09/2021 - 01/10/2021	Presentation - “DeepRank-GNN: A Graph Neural Network Framework to Learn Interaction Patterns from Protein-Protein Interfaces” at Graphism & Molecular Modelling / French Cheminformatics Society meeting	100
11/10/2021 - 15/10/2021	Lectures and Practical - “Exploring protein docking with HADDOCK” at EMBL-EBI Structural Bioinformatics course	30
18/10/2021 - 21/10/2021	Presentation - “Shape-restrained modelling of protein-small molecule complexes with HADDOCK” at BioExcel Conference / EMBO Workshop Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulations	166
19/10/2021 - 21/10/2021	Presentations - “WeNMR under EGI: A 10+ years happy symbiosis” and “WeNMR project: boosting structural biology research with DIRAC services” at the European Grid Infrastructure (EGI) Conference 2021	200
09/11/2021	BioExcel Webinar - “Computationally designing therapeutic antibodies - combining immune repertoire data and structural information”	86
09/12/2021	BioExcel Webinar - X3DNA-DSSR, a resource for structural bioinformatics of nucleic acids	79

15/12/2021 - 17/12/2021	Keynote presentation - “Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes” at the 5th International Symposium on Bioinformatics	700
21/03/2022 - 25/03/2022	Presentation - “Customizable Integrative Modelling Workflows with HADDOCK3” at the International Symposium on Grids & Clouds 2022	200
28/03/2022 - 01/04/2022	Lectures - “Docking Basics” and HADDOCK Tutorial at the BioExcel School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
09/05/2022 - 14/05/2022	Lecture - “Combining different sources of experimental data in modelling” at FEBS workshop: Lost in Integration - Probing Biomolecules with Electrons, Photons, Neutrons and Magnetic Spins	45
23/05/2022 - 25/05/2022	HADDOCK workshop at Pázmány Péter Catholic University	40
07/06/2022	BioExcel Webinar - Introducing HADDOCK3. Enabling modular integrative modelling pipelines	44
06/06/2022 - 09/06/2022	Presentation - “Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes” at the Modern trends in targeted structure-based drug design and discovery KAUST Research Conference	60
10/06/2021	Instruct-ERIC Software Developers Exchange Webinar - “Modular code for a module software: developing HADDOCK3”	
13/06/2022 - 17/06/2022	Lectures - “Docking Basics” and HADDOCK Tutorial at the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
Total number of community member participations:		3044

Table 3: integrative modelling community events participated in during PM19-PM42 with number of confirmed participants where known.

Table 4 below shows a summary of recordings of lectures, demonstrations, presentations, and editions of the BioExcel webinar series relevant to the integrative modelling community hosted on [our YouTube channel](#), and the views these recordings accrued during the period PM19-PM42 - regardless of whether they were published during that period, or prior. In total such recordings accrued around 10 000 views.

Recording	Published	Views accrued during PM19 - PM42
BioExcel Webinar #36: Prediction of protein-protein interactions in CAPRI	PM7	511

BioExcel Webinar #45: PDB-Dev: A prototype system for archiving integrative structures	PM17	173
BioExcel Webinar #46: The HADDOCK 2.4 server - new features and a guided demo	PM18	2730
BioExcel Webinar #47: COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub	PM18	294
Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes - Part 1 (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	1468
Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes - Part 2 (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	415
HADDOCK-based drug repurposing screening for COVID-19 (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	286
When HADDOCK meets GROMACS (BioExcel Winter School 2020)	PM24	316
Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes - Part 1 (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	922
Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes - Part 2 (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	318
Molecular dynamics meet docking: A use case on antibody design (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	541
BioExcel Webinar #57: Computationally designing therapeutic antibodies	PM35	945
BioExcel Webinar #59: X3DNA-DSSR, a resource for structural bioinformatics of nucleic acids	PM36	400
Basics of docking and introduction to HADDOCK (PRACE Autumn School: Fundamentals of Biomolecular Simulations and Virtual Drug Development) , hosted by Bulgarian National Centre for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system	PM40	123
HADDOCK demonstrations and hands-on session (PRACE Autumn School: Fundamentals of Biomolecular Simulations and Virtual Drug Development) , hosted by Bulgarian National Centre for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system	PM40	32
BioExcel Webinar #67: Introducing HADDOCK3. Enabling modular integrative modelling pipelines	PM42	63
Total views:		9537

Table 4: recordings relevant to the integrative modelling community available via the BioExcel YouTube channel, and the number of views they accrued during PM19-PM42.

In-depth Support

We have supported researchers performing integrative modelling (and those considering doing so) through many of the community participation events listed

above, including current and potential future users of HADDOCK, through Q&A sessions, direct discussions, and by email with participants after these events. BioExcel has continued to offer support via the AskBioExcel forum, where we have addressed over 300 in-depth user queries, mostly regarding HADDOCK but including our other supported software relevant to the community: [DISVIS](#) and [PRODIGY](#). **Figure 3** shows pageview statistics of the AskBioExcel forum over the entire lifetime of BioExcel-2 (PM1-PM42). This clearly demonstrates that the number of views of resolved in-depth user queries regarding usage of HADDOCK and guidance on docking in general by both registered users as well as anonymous non-registered users grew noticeably in PM19-PM42 compared to PM1-PM18. Visibility of the forum to various automatic indexing crawlers that amongst other things feed search engines also increased.

Figure 3: AskBioExcel forum pageviews (mostly HADDOCK support) during PM1-PM42. Peaks during June 2020/21/22, November/December 2020, and March 2022 correspond to usage of the forum for BioExcel Summer/Winter Schools.

Best Practice

The Best Practices guide for HADDOCK has been available since November 2020 (PM23) at <https://bonvinlab.org/software/bpg>. Since then, it is the second most visited page of the bonvinlab.org website (after the education page holding all the tutorials), with ~14 000 page views.

User & Community Needs Analysis and Feedback

Summary of HADDOCK web server user survey metrics and impact

We continued operating an ongoing survey amongst users of the HADDOCK web server portal and gathered 1093 responses during the period PM19-PM42. Dividing this period into two roughly equal periods, namely PM19-PM31 (614 responses) and PM32-PM42 (479 responses) and comparing survey results between them as shown in **Table 5**, shows there were some differences between the two periods and that these mainly indicate improvements in key metrics, which we take as evidence of positive impact of work done during BioExcel-2.

	average score or % “Yes” over PM19 - PM31	average score or % “Yes” over PM32 - PM42
Did you manage to successfully submit a job via the portal?	97%	96%
How would you rate the reliability of the web portal? 0 = “Never works” 5 = “Always works”	4.30	4.37
How would you rate the user friendliness of the web portal interface? 0 = “Poor” 5 = “Excellent”	4.42	4.41
How would you rate the side documentation of the submission interface? 0 = “No at all useful” 5 = “Very useful”	4.22	4.28
How do you like the new 2.4 portal compared to the old 2.2 one (if you used it)? 0 = “Much worse, give me back the old one” 5 = “Much better, it was time to change!”	4.16	4.29
Are you aware of the online software manual for HADDOCK (bonvinlab.org/software/haddock2.4)? (“Yes” or “No”)	70%	76%
Have you been using any of our online tutorials available from bonvinlab.org/education? (“Yes” or “No”)	47%	53%
Are you aware HADDOCK is a core software of the BioExcel Centre of Excellence? (“Yes” or “No”)	56%	57%
Are you aware HADDOCK is making use of high-throughput distributed computing resources of EGI/EOSC (grid computing)? (“Yes” or “No”)	44%	45%
Are you using or have you used a local version of HADDOCK? “Yes” or “No”	17%	21%
Would you recommend the new web portal of HADDOCK to your collaborators? “Yes”, “No”, or “Maybe” (percentage shown here is “Yes”)	87%	89%

Table 5: HADDOCK web portal survey user survey metrics for two periods: PM19-PM31 and PM32-PM42. Cells in green indicate improvements in key metrics going from the earlier to the later period.

Compared to the previous reporting period, improvements were found in the fraction of respondents who were aware of the HADDOCK manual and the fraction who had been using our online tutorials, which both grew by 6%, which we take as evidence that a combination of the manual and tutorial content we produced within BioExcel and how we disseminated these had a noticeable impact on improving how well our users feel supported. Encouragingly, the survey results also show a 4% higher uptake willingness of users to use a version of HADDOCK installed on locally available compute resources in addition to using the web portal.

Compared to the previous reporting period, the HADDOCK web portal was also experienced as being slightly more reliable on average, the documentation provided alongside the submission interface was deemed on average to have improved slightly, and more users preferred the newer portal. A slightly higher percentage than an already very high fraction of users in the earlier period said they would recommend the HADDOCK web portal to collaborators.

Evidence of impact from detailed HADDOCK web server user survey feedback

Users were asked to provide a free text response to several questions, including what they thought about the user friendliness of the web server portal, why they rated the new 2.4 version of the HADDOCK web server compared to the older version 2.2. the way they did, and whether they had any suggestions for improvements or any other comments. The responses, which can be found in Appendix 1, included detailed positive feedback that confirmed the impact of our work developing the web server and the portal interface, and the value to users of HADDOCK's availability as a web service. Overall positive feedback on the HADDOCK web server and its usability included the following comments:

“Generates most reliable results and most user-friendly docking software I have used so far.”

“Having HADDOCK online and freely accessible with all of the support forums make it very easy to use and I train students to use it in combination with their NMR or low resolution cryoEM, SAXS, etc. The support, openness, history, and efficiency of the server make it one of the best.”

“I can't wait to compare your program to our previously determined RosettaDock complex! Thank you for making a user-friendly portal which is much easier than Rosetta in my opinion.”

“Great platform, thanks a lot for providing this! “

Furthermore, positive feedback comparing the new HADDOCK version 2.4 web server to the older version 2.2 included the following comments that confirmed the impact of our work and appreciation from users:

“The workspace is very useful. Furthermore, I like the fact that you receive error messages before your final submission :)”

“The 2.4 portal provides the user with information about where uploads fail in a clear manner before proceeding to further steps. The new portal also provides information about what default parameters change if certain selections are made in a previous step.”

“Clearer error messages, visualization, feedback regarding upload files, direct interaction with inputs and parameters. Nice!”

Detailed actionable feedback from HADDOCK web server user survey

Detailed feedback from users over the period PM19-PM42 provided us with ample concrete suggestions to improve the HADDOCK web server functionality and portal user interface, and the general provision of guidance to HADDOCK users. This feedback - included in full in Appendix 1 - highlighted the importance of the following areas, in rough order of priority based on feedback frequency:

- Provision of additional quick inline help within portal interface in the form of mouseover tips or hyperlinks to relevant parts in external documentation regarding portal use, input specification / preparation and especially the meaning of and suitable selection of docking parameters
- Provision of ample worked examples and tutorials
- Increased flexibility in input formats and constraints on docking runs
- Partially automated preparation of provided inputs for docking runs
- Improvement of error handling and messages
- Additional information about and control of job execution

These insights into the needs of our users helped drive us to create additional tutorials and documented best practice and to actively promote these, together with the HADDOCK manual, thanks to which we achieved the greater use of both as evidenced in the preceding section. We also implemented more strict validation of the input data / parameters and molecule type-specific settings on the web portal.

Classical Molecular Modelling & Simulation (GROMACS & PMX)

Community Participation

During the period PM19-PM42 BioExcel (co-)organised and participated in a number of events in which we engaged with and/or supported at least 2400 members of the community interested in classical molecular modelling and simulation, including both current and potential future users of GROMACS and

PMX, as shown in **Table 6**. Due to the pandemic most events in this period took place online.

Date	Event and participation	Participants
03/09/2020 - 04/09/2020	Lectures & tutorials on molecular dynamics simulation, free energy calculations, and GROMACS at SNIC / PRACE / BioExcel workshop: Introduction to GROMACS	54
13/09/2020 - 16/09/2020	CECAM Summer workshop: “Multiscale simulations and biological channels”	20
15/09/2020	BioExcel Student Webinar: Summer School 2020 Edition	43
20/10/2020	Seminar presentation - “Alchemical free energy calculations for stability and affinity predictions” at University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign Theoretical and Computational Biophysics Group	20
30/11/2020 - 04/12/2020	Lectures - “Basis of molecular dynamics simulations”, “Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced-sampling methods”, “Cryo-EM vs stereochemistry”, “Introduction to free energy calculations”, and Tutorials - “A guide to perform MD simulation with GROMACS”, “Metadynamics - a guided introduction”, and Presentation - “When HADDOCK meets GROMACS” at the BioExcel Winter School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
12/01/2021 - 15/02/2021	Presentations and hands-on demonstrations - “Using umbrella-sampling (“pulling”) simulations”, “Using replica-exchange molecular dynamics”, “Using applied-weight histogram methods (“AWH”)”, and “Computing trajectories efficiently on GPUs”, at BioExcel/ENCCS workshop Advanced topics in simulations with GROMACS	30
18/01/2021	BioExcel Student Webinar: Winter School 2020 Edition	38
01/02/2021 - 03/02/2021	Lectures and hands-on exercises - “GROMACS - Python down to the metal interface for in-memory toolchains with GROMACS”, “pmx - free energy calculations or other”, and “Performant setup of GROMACS on GPUs” at BioExcel/PRACE/CSC Advanced GROMACS workshop	18
18/02/2021	BioExcel Webinar - What’s new in GROMACS 2021	96
11/03/2021	BioExcel Webinar - NB-LIB: A performance portable library for computing forces and energies of multi-particle systems	41
17/03/2021 - 18/03/2021	Lectures and hands-on practicals - “Atomistic MD Algorithm”, “Algorithm improvements and HPC”, “MD Simulation Setup”, “Introduction to coarse-grained simulation”, “Application examples: HPC against COVID-19”, “Trajectory visualization”, “Trajectory analysis” at PATC course: Introduction to Simulation Environments for Life Sciences	30
22/03/2021 - 23/03/2021	Practical - “Benchmarking Molecular Dynamics Performance Using GROMACS” at PRACE/BioExcel course: Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists	20
30/03/2021	BioExcel Webinar #54: Applying the Accelerated Weight Histogram method to alchemical transformations	91

07/04/2021 - 09/04/2021	Presentation on BioExcel UC1 - “Molecular Dynamics meets Docking: A use case on antibody design” at CINECA course: High Performance Molecular Dynamics	60
08/04/2021	Presentation - “BioExcel-CV19: a database of COVID-19 related Molecular Dynamics trajectories” at CECAM Mixed-gen Session 4: Data Driven Science	100
23/04/2021 - 24/04/2021	Huenfeld 2021 Workshop on Computer Simulation and Theory of Macromolecules	37
25/04/2021 - 28/04/2021	Presentation - “The molecular dynamics of potassium channel gating” at WE-Heraeus Stiftung Workshop on Advanced Physical and Computational Techniques to Investigate Protein Dynamics	80
09/06/2021	Presentation - “BioExcel toolbox: advanced applications for molecular modelling simulations” at 1st Norwegian Computer Aided Molecular Design (NorCAMD) Community Event	60
07/06/2021 - 11/06/2021	Lectures - “Basis of molecular dynamics simulations”, “Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced-sampling methods”, “Introduction to free energy calculations”, “Applications of alchemical free energy calculations” and Tutorials - “A guide to perform MD simulation with GROMACS”, “Metadynamics - a guided introduction”, and PMX tutorial at BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
15/06/2021 - 17/06/2021	Presentation on “Alchemical Absolute Protein-Ligand Binding Free Energies for Drug Design” at 2020 Workshop on Free Energy Methods in Drug Design	500
09/09/2021 - 10/09/2021	Lectures - “Introduction to MD using GROMACS”, “GROMACS features”, “Accelerated Weight Histogram”, “GROMACS GPU performance” and Tutorials - “Basic MD tutorial”, “DNA Base Flipping AWH tutorial” at GROMACS workshop: a collaboration between BioExcel and National EuroHPC Competence Centre Portugal	68
20/09/2021 - 24/09/2021	Lectures - “Best practices and Q&A session on HPC usage of GROMACS for biomolecular simulations”, “Introduction to free energy calculations with PMX” and demonstrations and hands-on session for working with PMX at PRACE Autumn School: Fundamentals of Biomolecular Simulations and Virtual Drug Development (hosted by Bulgarian National Center for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system)	165
28/09/2021	SBGrid Consortium Webinar on GROMACS	30
18/10/2021 - 21/10/2021	BioExcel Conference / EMBO Workshop Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulations	166
23/11/2021	BioExcel Webinar #58: CHARMM Force Field Development History, Features, and Implementation in GROMACS	192
31/01/2022 - 02/02/2022	Practical - “Benchmarking molecular dynamics performance using GROMACS” at PRACE/BioExcel/PerMedCoE course: Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists	27
04/02/2022 - 06/02/2022	“Hands-on Molecular Dynamics with GROMACS on Discoverer: running efficient jobs and building GROMACS from source” at PRACE Course: HPC	58

	Fundamentals for End Users (hosted by Bulgarian National Center for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system)	
07/02/2022 - 09/02/2022	Lectures - “Overview of enhanced sampling methods”, “Accelerated weight histogram (AWH) method”, “Performance considerations, CPU + GPU”, and hands-on tutorials: “AWH”, “Efficient use of GPU” at BioExcel / CSC / ENCCS Advanced GROMACS workshop	26
08/03/2022	BioExcel Webinar #61: What’s new in GROMACS 2022	101
09/03/2022 - 10/03/2022	Lectures and practicals on using Bennett Acceptance Ratio and Accelerated Weighted Histogram methods for alchemical free energy calculations at Virtual course on free energy calculation and alchemical transformation in GROMACS	27
28/03/2022 - 01/04/2022	Lectures - “Basis of molecular dynamics simulations”, “Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced-sampling methods”, “Introduction to free energy calculations”, “Applications of alchemical free energy calculations” and Tutorials - “A guide to perform MD simulation with GROMACS”, “Metadynamics - a guided introduction”, and PMX tutorial at the BioExcel School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
05/04/2022	BioExcel Webinar #62: Improvements in the GROMACS heterogeneous parallelization	66
21/04/2022	BioExcel Webinar #63: GROMACS/pmx for large scale alchemical protein-ligand binding affinity screening (presentation of UC5 work)	70
13/06/2022 - 17/06/2022	Lectures - “Molecular dynamics basics”, “Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced-sampling methods”, and GROMACS and PMX tutorials at BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
Total number of community member participations:		2417

Table 6: classical molecular modelling & simulation community events participated in during PM19-PM42 with number of confirmed participants where known.

Amongst the events in **Table 6** are a number of workshops at both basic and advanced levels that were (co-)organised by BioExcel in collaboration with national and pan-European HPC centres and infrastructure including CSC Finland, the Portuguese and Swedish National EuroCC HPC Competence Centres, PRACE, and the Bulgarian National Centre for Supercomputing Applications (supporting users of the new EuroHPC Discoverer system):

- [SNIC / PRACE / BioExcel workshop: Introduction to GROMACS](#)
- [BioExcel/ENCCS workshop: Advanced topics in simulations with GROMACS](#)
- [BioExcel/PRACE/CSC Advanced GROMACS workshop](#)
- [PRACE Autumn School: Fundamentals of Biomolecular Simulations and Virtual Drug Development](#) (hosted by Bulgarian National Centre for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system)
- [GROMACS workshop: a collaboration between BioExcel and National EuroHPC Competence Centre Portugal](#)

- [PRACE/BioExcel/PerMedCoE course: Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists](#)
- [PRACE Course: HPC Fundamentals for End Users](#) (hosted by Bulgarian National Center for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system)
- [BioExcel / CSC / ENCCS Advanced GROMACS workshop](#)

During most of these events and also especially at the BioExcel Summer and Winter Schools, direct contact with the attendees was built via living shared documents, the BioExcel forum, and by email in order to provide a channel to engage with attendees, understand their needs, and target support to individual attendees. Most of these events generated lecture and tutorial materials freely available online to the community. Through pre-production access, BioExcel assisted NCSA Bulgaria by ensuring a build of GROMACS optimal for the hardware and software stack of the new EuroHPC Discoverer machine was in place for users. We also benchmarked GROMACS performance to ascertain optimal execution protocol on Discoverer and [shared this best practice](#) with users at the [PRACE Course: HPC Fundamentals for End Users](#) as a hands-on practical following a high level introductory overview of GROMACS.

BioExcel has also engaged with the classical molecular modelling and simulation community by sharing experience from Use Case 1 work as a presentation “Molecular Dynamics meets Docking: A use case on antibody design” at the [CINECA course: High Performance Molecular Dynamics](#), and Use Case 5 in [BioExcel Webinar #63: GROMACS/pmx for large scale alchemical protein-ligand binding affinity screening](#), at BioExcel Winter and Summer Schools, as well as at other community events, as described in detail in deliverable [D3.6 - Pre-exascale showcase calculation and final Use Case report](#).

The BioExcel webinar series featured 20 webinars of specific interest to the classical molecular modelling and simulation community. Altogether these had 1639 live attendees and over 15 000 YouTube views by PM42. As part these series, the GROMACS team introduced what was new in each yearly GROMACS release, and gave seminars about new GROMACS features such as the accelerated weighted histogram (AWH) method for alchemical transformation, and hybrid parallelization in GROMACS. The most popular tools and topics external to BioExcel were MDanalysis and the CHARMM port to GROMACS.

Table 7 below shows a summary of recordings of lectures, demonstrations, presentations, and editions of the BioExcel webinar series relevant to the classical molecular modelling and simulation community hosted on [our YouTube channel](#), and the views these recordings accrued during the period PM19-PM42 - regardless of whether they were published during that period, or prior. In total such recordings accrued over 33 000 views. In addition to our BioExcel channel-hosted recordings, an [SBGrid consortium webinar on GROMACS](#) published on the SBGrid consortium’s YouTube channel September 2021 (PM33) gained around 3000 views by PM42.

Recording	Published	Views accrued during PM19 - PM42
BioExcel Webinar #35: GROMACS 2019 – overview of the new features and capabilities	PM5	145
BioExcel Webinar #37: More bang for your buck: Improved use of GPUs for GROMACS 2018	PM9	170
BioExcel Webinar #38: Enhanced molecular simulations with PLUMED	PM9	1006
BioExcel Webinar #39: Accelerating sampling in GROMACS with the AWH method	PM9	1257
BioExcel Webinar #41: A walk through simulation parameter options (.mdp files) for GROMACS	PM12	2394
BioExcel Webinar #42: What's new in GROMACS 2020	PM14	292
BioExcel Webinar #43: Density guided simulations	PM16	416
BioExcel Webinar #44: Clustering free energy landscapes from molecular dynamics simulations	PM17	2041
Basis of molecular dynamics simulations - Part I (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	4977
Basis of molecular dynamics simulations - Part 2 (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	1658
Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced sampling methods Part I (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	398
Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced sampling methods Part II (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	197
GROMACS Features and Future (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	336
Identifying EGFR mutations causing drug resistance (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	203
Alchemy for protein-protein binding (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	235
Introduction to free energy calculations (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	1689
Applications of alchemical free energy calculations (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	1303
Cryo-EM densities vs Stereochemistry (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	96

BioExcel Webinar #47: COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub	PM18	294
BioExcel Webinar #49: Molecular movies made easy with Molywood	PM22	731
BioExcel Student Webinar: Winter School 2020 Edition	PM25	290
BioExcel Webinar #52: What's new in GROMACS 2021	PM26	892
BioExcel Webinar #53: NB-LIB: A performance portable library for computing forces and energies	PM27	197
BioExcel Webinar #54: Applying the Accelerated Weight Histogram method to alchemical transformations	PM28	886
Basis of molecular dynamics simulations - Part I (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	1645
Basis of molecular dynamics simulations - Part II (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	728
Constant pH molecular dynamics in GROMACS (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	1032
Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced-sampling methods - Part I (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	267
Modelling molecular recognition through enhanced-sampling methods - Part II (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	288
Alchemical free energy calculations using pmx (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	781
Molecular dynamics meet docking: A use case on antibody design (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	543
Accelerating sampling in GROMACS with the Accelerated Weight Histogram method (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	409
BioExcel Student Webinar: Summer School 2021 Edition	PM34	185
BioExcel Webinar #55: MDAnalysis, interoperable analysis of biomolecular simulations in Python	PM35	1184
BioExcel Webinar #58: CHARMM Force Field Development History, Features and Implementation in GROMACS	PM35	1146
BioExcel Webinar #61: What's new in GROMACS 2022	PM38	777
Optimization of efflux avoidance and inhibition for antibiotic development (BioExcel 2022 School)	PM40	35
Bending torsional elasticity and energetics of the plus end microtubule tip (BioExcel 2022 School)	PM40	40
Getting good performance in GROMACS default (BioExcel 2022 School)	PM40	198
Basics of Molecular Dynamics (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	78

Introduction to Molecular Dynamics simulations with GROMACS (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	115
Demonstrations on how to prepare and run an MD simulation with GROMACS on a supercomputer (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	117
GROMACS HPC usage best practices and Q&A session (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	50
Introduction to free energy calculations with PMX (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	98
PMX demonstration and hands-on session (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	59
Application of molecular dynamics simulations in the field of drug discovery (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	87
Different approaches for finding ligands inhibiting the NSP10/NSP16 complex of the SARS-CoV-2 virus (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	41
In silico study of the anti-inflammatory action of heparin within the Covid-19 context (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	32
Beyond in silico simulations: a case study on acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	40
Could FE calculations with GROMACS be faster? (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	158
Clustering of doxorubicin and its interaction with bio-polymers (alginates) (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	49
Molecular dynamics simulations of fenofibrata solubilization into bile salt and fatty acids micelles (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	108
Selectivity of binding of vector molecules to folate receptor-alpha observed by molecular dynamics (PRACE / NCSA Bulgaria 2021 Autumn School)	PM40	142
BioExcel Webinar #62: Improvements in the GROMACS heterogeneous parallelization	PM40	202
BioExcel Webinar #63 - GROMACS/pmx large-scale alchemical protein-ligand binding affinity screening	PM40	345
BioExcel Student Webinar: School 2022 Edition	PM41	344
Total views:		33 426

Table 7: recordings relevant to the classical molecular modelling and simulation community available via the BioExcel YouTube channel, and the number of views they accrued during PM19-PM42.

In-depth Support

In-depth support was carried out on multiple levels, comprising forum, mailing list, personal interactions, specialist tech support and site visits. To better support users, the GROMACS user mailing list was moved in May 2020 to a more modern forum format with extended capabilities (located at gromacs.bioexcel.eu). The forum has on average 25 topics per week, but a constant increase in the number of new contributors of 10 units per week. During the period PM19-PM42 we addressed around 1000 in-depth support queries from forum users. **Figure 4** below shows the number of pageviews of logged-in users, anonymous users and crawlers.

All reports | Consolidated Pageviews ?

Figure 4: GROMACS forum statistics (pageviews)

The forum is divided in 3 categories: “User discussion”, “Announcement” and “Third party tools and files category”. The first two focus on GROMACS, the last one provides the opportunity to announce and discuss third party tools and files relevant for the GROMACS community. In March 2021 we implemented topic ‘tag’ (e.g. free-energy, gpu, system set-up, etc), to provide the correct visibility to the posts, to facilitate users searching among posts and to indirectly target experts (avoiding personal tagging). In the context of BioExcel, a qm-mm and pmx tag were recently created. The forum allows us to trace the major user issues, but users’ interests. Here information on the most referenced topics (topics that have received the most views) and trending search terms have been very useful. For example ‘free-energy’, ‘gpu’ and ‘awh’ can be found among the 10 most searched terms from PM19 to PM42.

To concretely feed user issues back into the development cycles, forum topics were cross-linked to issues logged in the GROMACS development platform GitLab, and these were tagged “request” to signal to the developers where and how users envision improved functionality.

To concretely address problems faced by GROMACS users, we have tuned GROMACS tutorial to user issues. The forum and the GROMACS survey already described in deliverable [D3.4 - User Community Support and Engagement Report \(halftime update\)](#) allowed us to understand where there is need for better documentation or information. For example, the introductory MD tutorial was extended to include the use of analysis tools, in response to the survey results and

topic popularity on the forum. To make the tutorial accessible to a wide community we implemented them in a Jupyter notebook and made them available online at tutorials.gromacs.org. The tutorials can be run online for free thanks to mybinder.org and [BioExcel Binder](https://bioexcel.binder.org).

Administrators and application support staff of (HPC) research computing centres often require more specialised and extended support efforts to compile and install GROMACS in a way that makes the most use of very specialised hardware resources. These interactions typically lead to long-standing collaborations and insights on both sides: by fine-tuning on current GROMACS versions, developers learn about the scaling and performance of GROMACS. Simultaneously, GROMACS developers give advice on the best hardware setup for performing simulations. This type of in-depth support was carried out, amongst others, with CSC in Finland, and the EuroCC National Competence Centre in Portugal, and the equivalent in Sweden (ENCCS).

The in-depth support for PMX users was provided via email, the BioExcel forum and direct communication at conferences and workshops. In addition, the PMX team worked closely with Janssen Pharmaceutica and AstraZeneca to establish and support free energy calculation workflows for the use in drug discovery projects, as described in more detail in the Industry community section of this document.

In order to make it easier to navigate among all the GROMACS related topics/information, we have also redesigned the official GROMACS website (www.gromacs.org).

Finally, having merged our experience in community participation and in-depth support, we discovered and subsequently made use of a rule of thumb for optimal community engagement and uptake when introducing a new software feature (e.g. a new simulation algorithm) to the community, namely:

1. Prepare a tutorial, to be used both online and in person
2. Introduce the new feature via a topical webinar that is also recorded and remains accessible
3. Point the community to the tutorial and forum whenever promoting the new functionality, e.g., when presenting results obtained with it
4. Create a specific tag on the support forum to better track and analyse in-depth support queries and hence better analyse user experiences, needs, issues, etc.
5. Provide a feature-specific workshop using the above material, tutorial, and webinar as starting point and including both presentations of results, protocol, and hands-on practical exercises for users to gain experience.

Best Practice

We have continued to update the [GROMACS Best Practice Guide](#) (BPG) during the period PM19-PM42.

In the performance cookbook section of the BPG we have added benchmark results and guidance for obtaining optimal performance on JUWELS BOOSTER, the number 11 HPC machine on the Top500 list at time of writing and the 3rd highest-capability machine in the EU according to Top500 metrics. This included guidance on the advantage to be gained using GROMACS' recent improved GPU offloading, and detailed advice including example job scripts on how to control GROMACS execution through process-to-core pinning so as to optimally take advantage of on-node hardware topology, as this was found to make a significant difference to performance. Following work on the EuroHPC Discoverer system through pre-production access, we shared results and performance advice for that system as part of the [PRACE Course: HPC Fundamentals for End Users](#) and also included this in the BPG performance cookbook. As part of this work we uncovered an [issue with the new experimental GPU Direct Communications support within GROMACS](#), which as a result has been resolved for subsequent GROMACS releases. Finally, we added guidance on how to efficiently perform benchmarking so as to help users on any system gauge for themselves how best to make use of available resources to run their particular simulations.

Based on analysis of the needs of our user community (see “User & Community Needs Analysis and Feedback” section below) we expanded the workflow section of the BPG to include guidance on postprocessing analysis of simulation trajectories using GROMACS tools.

The MPG team was involved in developing multiple best practice guides pertaining to free energy calculations. One practical guide addressing common caveats in alchemical free energy calculations is currently in progress.

User & Community Needs Analysis and Feedback

During this reporting period we continued to make ongoing adjustments to content and presentation of training materials as well as decisions on relevant webinars and other events to organise based on our engagement with users through the forum and at events, as reported in “Community Participation” and “In-depth Support” sections above.

We also performed standalone work explicitly analysing needs of the classical molecular modelling & simulation community, focusing in particular on where we can have the biggest impact, namely amongst the sizeable community of GROMACS users. Our large-scale survey of GROMACS users already reported in deliverable [D3.4 - User Community Support and Engagement Report \(halftime update\)](#) highlighted that usage of GROMACS postprocessing analysis tools is an important time-consuming and occasionally frustrating point of user's experience with GROMACS, and that additional documentation is desirable. During PM19-PM42 we followed up by performing an in-depth analysis of posts on the GROMACS forum already tagged with “analysis-tools” as a topic to substantiate this and to identify and prioritise which particular aspects of tool usage and issues faced would be most impactful to provide additional guidance on. The total number of queries matching this tag was relatively low since the forum analysis was performed in PM30, by which point GROMACS support had transitioned to

the forum from the historical mailing list only 13 months earlier. However the list of concrete topics found matched priorities earlier identified in our large-scale user survey and provided not only confirmation but also detailed insights into what most support was needed on. In descending order of priority based on the frequency with which users submitted support queries on the topic, the topics identified were:

- Inter-particle distance (9 queries)
 - How to calculate between residue and ligand
 - How to calculate distance from specific (x,y,z) in sim box
 - Bond length distribution (2 queries)
 - Telling whether two proteins are interacting with one another
 - Protein end-to-end distances
 - Distance from COM of a group of atoms
 - `gmx mindist`, `gmx pairdist`, `gmx distance`
 - Using `gmx mindist`
- Free energy calculations (6 queries)
 - Binding free energy
 - Measuring free energy
 - Solvation free energy
 - Using `gmx lie`
 - Also, entropy calcs using `gmx covar` and `gmx ana eig`
- How to use `gmx cluster` (5 queries)
 - `gmx clustsize`
 - How to output multiple cluster info
 - Extract positions of atoms within a specific cluster
- Intermolecular hydrogen bonding (5 queries)
 - in general
 - Specifically in water models
 - Calculating bond time
 - Histogram binning
 - bond calculation for simulation sub-region
- RMSF/RMSD how-to (5 queries)
 - What is the purpose/how to optimise runs based on this?
 - Clustering analysis based on this.
- MSD/VACF (5 queries)
 - Diffusion constant calculations/link to VACF (could be possible example)
 - Diffusion constant calc from MSD (both GROMACS version & "by hand")
 - Does MSD use COM of particle? How to enable/disable
 - Setting tau to not OOM when calculating MSD of long runs.
- RDFs (4 queries)
 - for complex systems
 - for COMs of proteins (how to determine different molecules with same resid)
 - Basics of RDFs (PBC vs non-PBC)
 - RDF from COM of particle
- How-to umbrella sampling (3 queries)

- Choosing distance between windows
- General how-to for non-specific system
- Using `gmx spatial` (2 queries)
- Various (1 query each):
 - Radius of gyration
 - Structure/compactness
 - Barostats/thermostats & noise
 - Calculating structure factors (using SANS)
 - How to use `gmx densmap`
 - 2D PCA scatter plots
 - Using `gmx potential`
 - PCA -- how to plot eigenvector indices.
 - Using `gmx sasa` (solvent accessible surface area)
 - Non-Gaussian parameters of displacement distribution
 - Plotting thermo properties vs time

We used this to prioritise our efforts in expanding the GROMACS BPG, and to decide which particular post-processing commands and topics to provide additional guidance on.

Hybrid QM/MM Molecular Modelling & Simulation (GROMACS+CP2K)

Community Participation

BioExcel (co-)organised and participated in a number of events in which we engaged with and/or supported at least 1700 members of the community interested in hybrid QM/MM molecular modelling and simulation, including both current and potential future users of CP2K - standalone or together with GROMACS through the BioExcel-developed GROMACS-CP2K interface - as shown in **Table 8**.

Date	Event and participation	Participants
13/20/2020 & 20/20/2020	Hands-on exercises on geometry optimisation methods, nudged elastic band, and a Diels-Alder reaction at the BioExcel / ARCHER2 course Practical Introduction to QM/MM using CP2K for biomolecular modelling	37
30/10/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop: Kickoff webinar	183
30/11/2020 - 04/12/2020	Lectures - "Introduction to QM/MM", and Tutorial "Introduction to QM/MM simulations: GROMACS-CP2K Interface" at the BioExcel Winter School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
13/11/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Validation of DFT functionals in QM/MM simulations of enzymatic reactions initiated by the nucleophilic attack	106
26/11/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Obtaining accurate structures and energies with QM/MM	121

08/12/2020	BioExcel Webinar #51: Multiscale QM/MM simulations: exploring chemical reactions using novel GROMACS/CP2K interface	123
10/12/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Studies on enzyme-catalysed reactions	73
14/12/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Towards chemical accuracy in QM/MM modelling of enzyme catalytic mechanisms and protein-ligand binding	201
08/01/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Multiscale Simulation of Monoaminergic System: Applications to Neurodegeneration	73
12/01/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Modelling catalytic mechanisms in carbohydrate-active enzymes with QM/MM MD methods	95
29/01/2020	BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop: Panel Session	110
01/02/2021 - 03/02/2021	Lectures and hands-on exercise - “QM/MM simulations with GROMACS and CP2K” at BioExcel/PRACE/CSC Advanced GROMACS workshop	18
25/02/2021 - 25/03/2021	Cecam: Simulation of open systems in Chemistry, Pharma, Food Science and Immuno-diagnostics: Rare-event methods at constant chemical potentials including constant pH - an E-CAM Industry Scoping Work	
22/03/2021 - 23/03/2021	Practical - “QM/MM Simulations Using CP2K” at PRACE/BioExcel course: Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists	20
22/04/2021 - 23/04/2021	Lectures - “Introduction to QM/MM” and Practicals - “GROMACS + CP2K” and “CP2K Parameters” at BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: “QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K”	29
07/06/2021 - 11/06/2021	Lectures - “Introduction to QM/MM” and Tutorial - “Introduction to QM/MM Simulations” at BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
27/09/2021	NHR Atomistic Simulations Lab seminar on BioExcel GROMACS-CP2K interface	28
19/10/2021 - 22/10/2021	Lecture - “An introduction into molecular dynamics simulations of proteins” and molecular dynamics tutorial and demonstration at FEBS 2021 Advanced Course: Computational Approaches to Understanding and Engineering Enzyme Catalysis	30
31/01/2022 - 02/02/2022	Practical - “QM/MM Simulations Using CP2K” at PRACE/BioExcel/PerMedCoE course: Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists	27
04/02/2022 - 06/02/2022	“Hands-on running CP2K on Discoverer” at PRACE Course: HPC Fundamentals for End Users (hosted by Bulgarian National Center for Supercomputing Applications and EuroHPC Discoverer system)	58
07/02/2022 - 09/02/2022	Lecture and hands-on exercises - “QM/MM simulations with GROMACS and CP2K” at the BioExcel / CSC / ENCCS Advanced GROMACS workshop	26

08/03/2022	Presentation of official release of GROMACS-CP2K QM/MM interface in BioExcel Webinar #61: What's new in GROMACS 2022	101
28/03/2022 - 01/04/2022	Lectures - "Introduction to QM/MM" and Tutorials - "Introduction to QM/MM simulations" at the BioExcel School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
10/05/2022	BioExcel Webinar #65: QM/MM Simulation of Fluorescent Proteins and Proton Dynamics (Presentation of Use Case 4 work)	61
24/05/2022	BioExcel Webinar #66: Efficient (GROMACS+)CP2K compute resource usage for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems	53
13/06/2022 - 17/06/2022	Lectures - "Introduction to QM/MM" and CP2K QM/MM Tutorial at BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations	30
Total number of community member participations:		1693

Table 8: QM/MM molecular modelling & simulation community events participated in during PM19-PM42 with number of confirmed participants where known.

Our QM/MM community participation activities during this period include a multitude of events in which we promoted the GROMACS-CP2K interface and related software for performing QM/MM simulation, trained and supported researchers in their use, and disseminated our QM/MM Use Case 4 research work. We received very positive feedback (see also deliverable [D4.4 - Final report on dissemination and training](#)), for example anecdotally from an attendee at the [BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K"](#) who was able to get significant in-depth advice from BioExcel experts during dedicated Q&A sessions:

"It was perfect. It is rare to get such quality for free. I was truly honored to be selected and to attend this workshop."

We organised a virtual workshop ["Best Practices in QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems"](#) in order to provide a platform for top-level researchers in the field to share their expertise and established best practices with regards to QM/MM simulation of biological systems with the wider community. Many other BioExcel activities relating to QM/MM - training, community participation and in-depth support - were focused specifically on usage of our core software, especially GROMACS and CP2K. This workshop in contrast dealt with more general issues surrounding QM/MM computational modelling and simulation methodology and its underpinning chemistry that are more or less agnostic of particular software implementations but absolutely critical to the usage of any of them. This was done because we identified a strong necessity to bring best practices to the attention of the community of biomolecular researchers whom we sought to support, many of whom are less experienced using QM/MM and may not have a background in computational chemistry. BioExcel considers being aware of best practices as a prerequisite for productive, scientifically impactful use of any software for QM/MM modelling and simulation of biomolecular systems, hence we invested

significant effort in this workshop. We brought together experts in the use of QM/MM for biomolecular systems based across the EU and beyond, namely Spain, UK, Portugal, Sweden, UK, Slovenia, and Russia.

Figure 5: Best Practices in QM/MM Simulation of Biomolecular Systems: panel session with expert invited speakers

The QM/MM best practice workshop sessions, which ran as a time-separated thematic webinar series followed by an interactive panel session, were attended live by a total of 962 people, and recordings of these sessions on our YouTube channel accrued around 8800 views during the period PM19-PM42. The workshop also resulted in a best practice guide, as we report in the section on Standards and Best Practice below.

Table 9 below shows a summary of recordings of lectures, demonstrations, presentations, and editions of the BioExcel webinar series relevant to the hybrid QM/MM molecular modelling and simulation community hosted on [our YouTube channel](#) as well as by others, and the views these recordings accrued during the period PM19-PM42 - regardless of whether they were published during that period, or prior. In total such recordings accrued over 25 000 views during the period.

Recording	Published	Views accrued during PM19 - PM42
Preparing to run biomolecular QM/MM simulations with CP2K using AmberTools Online	PM17	1800

Introduction to QM/MM - Part 1 (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	3779
Introduction to QM/MM - Part 2 (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	1238
Practical introduction to QM/MM using CP2K for biomolecular modelling - Session 1 , hosted by UK ARCHER2 HPC service	PM22	982
Practical introduction to QM/MM using CP2K for biomolecular modelling - Session 2 , hosted by UK ARCHER2 HPC service	PM22	455
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop: Kick-off webinar	PM23	1327
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Validation of DFT functionals in QM/MM simulations of enzymatic reactions	PM23	821
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Obtaining accurate structures and energies with QM/MM	PM23	1252
BioExcel Webinar #51: Multiscale QM/MM: exploring chemical reactions using GROMACS/CP2K interface	PM24	1342
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Studies on enzyme-catalysed reactions	PM24	802
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Towards chemical accuracy in QM/MM modelling of enzyme catalytic mechanisms and protein-ligand binding	PM24	2400
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Multiscale Simulation of Monoaminergic System: Applications to Neurodegeneration	PM25	362
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop webinar: Modelling catalytic mechanisms in carbohydrate-active enzymes with QM/MM methods	PM25	1267
BioExcel QM/MM Best Practice workshop: Panel Session	PM25	503
Introduction to QM/MM - Part 3 (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM28	416
QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - Q&A 1 (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	342
QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - Practical 1 (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	2021
QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - Q&A 2 (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	193
QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - Practical 2 (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	651
QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - Q&A 3 (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	69
QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - CP2K parameters practical (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: "QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	562

QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - Practical 3 (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: “QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	392
QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K - Q&A 4 and wrapup (BioExcel / ARCHER2 course: “QM/MM simulation with GROMACS + CP2K)	PM29	147
Introduction to QM/MM - Part 1 (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	280
Introduction to QM/MM - Part 2 (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	224
NHR Atomistic Simulations Lab Seminar on the GROMACS-CP2K interface , hosted by the Paderborn Center for Parallel Computing	PM34	290
BioExcel Webinar #61: What’s new in GROMACS 2022 (QM/MM interface)	PM39	783
BioExcel Webinar #65: QM/MM Simulation of Fluorescent Proteins and Proton Dynamics	PM41	202
BioExcel Webinar #66: Efficient (GROMACS+)CP2K compute resource usage for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems	PM41	175
Total views:		25 077

Table 9: recordings relevant to the hybrid QM/MM molecular modelling and simulation community available via the BioExcel and other YouTube channels, and the number of views they accrued during PM19-PM42.

In-depth Support

Users have been supported with questions relating to performing QM/MM simulations of biomolecular systems with GROMACS+CP2K on the [QM/MM section of the AskBioExcel support forum](#). As expected of software functionality that is still relatively new and has only recently become available in an official GROMACS release - [starting with GROMACS 2022, released PM34](#) - the number of queries submitted to the AskBioExcel forum has been relatively low (a few each month), however this is higher than during the previous reporting period PM1-PM18. Since the incorporation of the GROMACS-CP2K QM/MM interface in an official GROMACS release we have seen relevant queries starting to appear in the GROMACS forum, where we have [started tagging them in order to better track and respond](#). We see this as a significant and noteworthy sign of increasing uptake, and know from experience that this increased visibility will continue to make users aware of the existence of the interface hence we expect uptake to continue to increase and mature.

In response to difficulties encountered setting up QM/MM simulations with GROMACS and CP2K, a number of users were provided with personal support through e-mail communication and Zoom meetings. Several national HPC computing centres across Europe were provided with assistance installing GROMACS/CP2K for general usage by any user of their HPC systems, including CSC-IT (Finland), SurfSARA (Netherlands) and EPCC (UK). Several groups from University of Oulu, Cambridge, Tallinn, and Izmir were provided with assistance

installing the GROMACS-CP2K interface onto their machines, including through testing and tutorial support.

Researchers at Imperial College in London were supported in their femtosecond X-ray crystallography experiments on reversibly photo switchable fluorescent proteins (rsFP), and 2 papers have been produced and submitted for review as a result. In collaboration with a group from KU Leuven, pilot simulations were carried out on new rsFP mutants with an initial aim to predict the effect of mutations on the folding, the absorption maxima, and the Stokes shift. In addition, a group from Cardiff University have been supported by providing both classical and QM/MM simulation parameters for fluorescent proteins.

Best Practice

As mentioned in the section on Community Participation above, we organised a [Workshop on Best Practices in QM/MM Simulation of Biomolecular Systems](#). Following the workshop we created a [Best Practice Guide for QM/MM Simulation of Biomolecular Systems](#) in order to capture and disseminate the outcomes of the workshop and provide a resource to the community to be used by researchers and referenced in training and support activities, thereby impacting not just users of GROMACS+CP2K but all community members interested in QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems, regardless of software used.

The guide is composed of two parts:

1. An overview and summary of best practices and advice on care that should be taken in all key aspects involved in QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems. This was based on topics covered in the workshops, and supplemented by background, references, and advice from BioExcel experts. It includes best practice guidance on what to consider when deciding whether to use QM/MM in the first place, on system preparation, method and level of theory, QM and QM-MM coupling treatments, simulation protocol, and validation and analysis of results.
2. A list of key points raised by the various invited expert speakers at the workshop, with time-indexed links to recordings from the workshop in which they give detailed advice on best practice based on their experience.

In addition to this new software-agnostic Best Practice Guide on QM/MM modelling and simulation methodology, we have updated and expanded the existing CP2K QM/MM Best Practice Guide that we published at PM24 and described in deliverable [D3.5 - Best Practice Guides](#). As planned and described in D3.5, we have extended this to include guidance on usage of the GROMACS-CP2K interface: [GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM Best Practice Guide](#). We have also added performance results, including parallel scaling efficiency, to help users understand what can be expected as obtainable GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM simulation performance on hardware architectures representative of those commonly found on modern HPC systems, including AMD EPYC processors and NVIDIA V100 GPUs

and for different QM treatments. These results were also shared in the [BioExcel webinar #66: Efficient \(GROMACS+\)CP2K compute resource usage for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems](#).

User & Community Needs Analysis and Feedback

Actionable feedback to drive GROMACS-CP2K interface development as well as the organisation of training and dissemination through events was derived from:

- The results of the QM/MM survey taken during the first half of the project
- Questions received during QM/MM-related webinars and training events
- Queries submitted on the [QM/MM section of the AskBioExcel forum](#) and, following the GROMACS 2022 release that incorporates the CP2K QM/MM interface, [relevant posts on the GROMACS forum \(tagged with 'qm-mm'\)](#).

According to results of the survey reported in deliverable [D3.4 - User Community Support and Engagement report \(halftime update\)](#), the majority (72%) of respondents in the field of biomolecular simulation had either considered using or already used QM/MM in their work. Most used or wanted to use QM/MM to study enzymatic reactions, protein-protein and/or protein-ligand binding. The largest single barrier to successful use of QM/MM according to 59% of respondents was the availability and/or quality of relevant practical tutorials. To address this need we developed several tutorials to show usage of CP2K and GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM usage, including both [basic](#) and more [advanced](#) levels. As well as delivering these at training events during PM19-PM42, we have made these available to users tutorials through the [GROMACS tutorials web portal](#).

The majority of survey respondents expressed wanting to study free energies of binding and reactions. To support such methods, we steered our WP1 interface development efforts during PM19-PM42 towards enabling efficient free energy simulations in conjunction with the GROMACS-CP2K interface. In particular, we adopted a highly parallelizable Accelerated Weight Histograms (AWH) method for performing reaction free-energy profile simulations into the QM/MM framework. This allows users to scan relevant multi-dimensional coordinate surfaces and obtain reaction profiles, for instance in enzymes.

One of the most common problems, according to feedback through abovementioned forums, discussion at training events, and direct requests by email, was installation of the GROMACS-CP2K interface. From having supported users installing the interface, we gathered typical problems encountered during installation. We then contacted and collaborated with the CP2K developers to greatly simplify the interface build procedure in order to streamline the user experience and facilitate uptake of the interface. We also provided additional installation guidance for CP2K and the GROMACS-CP2K interface [in the GROMACS manual](#) and [in the GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM best practice guide](#).

Another question frequently encountered when training and supporting users was regarding usage of compute resources to run GROMACS together with CP2K

to perform QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems. In particular, many users and groups actively using GROMACS are aware of the benefits of using GPU acceleration for GROMACS performance, especially given recent GPU offloading developments during BioExcel-2. Users therefore wondered whether CP2K is also capable of running on GPUs and whether doing so is advantageous when performing QM/MM simulations of biomolecular systems, be it with CP2K standalone or together with GROMACS. To directly address these questions from the community we delivered an overview in [BioExcel webinar #66: Efficient \(GROMACS+\)CP2K compute resource usage for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems](#). We also added examples to the [GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM Best Practice Guide](#) to help users understand what can be expected as obtainable GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM simulation performance and parallel scaling efficiency on hardware architectures representative of those commonly found on modern HPC systems, including AMD EPYC processors and NVIDIA V100 GPUs, and for different choices of QM treatments.

Workflow Tools & Standards (CWL and biobb)

Community Participation

BioExcel (co-)organised and participated in a number of events in which we engaged with and/or supported at least 4200 members of the community interested in using or developing workflow tools and standards, including both current and potential future users of the BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB) library, CWL, and related software such as (Py)COMPSs - as shown in **Table 10**.

Date	Event and participation	Participants
09/03/2020 - 13/03/2020	Automated Workflow Composition in the Life Sciences at Lorentz Center for Scientific Workshops in All Disciplines https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.54159.1	45
06/07/2020 - 10/07/2020	PyCOMPSs poster presentation at SciPy 2020	1500
16/07/2020	CECAM The importance of being H.P.C. Earnest webinar: "BioExcel Building Blocks and HPC: a Test Case in COVID Research"	100
04/09/2020	Presentation on BioExcel, PyCOMPSs and ML - " Dislib: parallelizing machine learning and its application to scientific applications " at Advances in computational modelling of cellular processes and high-performance computing, 19th European Conference on Computational Biology	110
16/09/2020 - 17/09/2020	Presentation of BioBB and PyCOMPSs - "Programming dynamic workflows in the Exascale era" at 14th RES Users Conference	
10/09/2020	BioExcel Webinar #48: Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks	48

9/11/2020 11/11/2020 13/11/2020	Presentations and hands-on exercises on BioBB at BioExcel course: Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel Building Blocks	18
01/11/2020 - 06/11/2020	Chairing of Vision Track at International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC)	600
9/11/2020 - 13/11/2020	ELIXIR BioHackathon Europe 2020	400
26/11/2020	Presentation on HPDA for biomolecular research: the BioExcel Case at EXDCI Workshop on AI and HPC convergence	85
27/11/2020 - 04/12/2020	International FAIR Convergence Symposium	300
30/11/2020 - 04/12/2020	Lectures - “BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB)”, “Computational biomolecular simulation workflows using BioBB”, Tutorial - “Protein-Complex MD Setup with Jupyter Notebooks and BioBB” and Presentation - “Using GROMACS and pmx with the BioBB library to tackle COVID-19 research” at the BioExcel Winter School 2020	30
13/01/2021	Workflows Community Summit #1 – Bringing the Scientific Workflows Community Together https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4606958	40
26/01/2021 - 27/01/2021	Overview of COMPSs at PATC Course: Programming Distributed Computing Platforms with COMPSs	
08/02/2021 - 10/02/2021	CWL Virtual Mini-Conference	
23/02/2021	9th Fenix Infrastructure webinar: Using ICEI resources for Atomistic Molecular Dynamics simulations	
01/03/2021 - 04/03/2021	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)	50
17/03/2021 - 18/03/2021	Hands-on exercises using BioBB at the PATC Course: Introduction to Simulation Environments for Life Sciences	30
30/03/2021 - 01/04/2021	Mini-workshop on FAIR principles at Software Sustainability Institute Collaborations Workshop 2021	
07/04/2021	Workflows Community Summit #2 – Advancing the State-of-the-art of Scientific Workflows Management Systems Research and Development https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915801	60
20/04/2021 - 23/04/2021	Participated in several workshops related to Standards and Best Practice at Research Data Alliance 17th Plenary	

06/06/2021 - 09/06/2021	Keynote presentation - “FAIR Computational Workflows” at Journées Ouvertes de Bioinformatique, Informatique et Mathématiques	400
07/06/2021 - 11/06/2021	Lectures - “BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB)”, “Computational biomolecular simulation workflows using BioBB”, Tutorial - “Protein-Complex MD Setup with Jupyter Notebooks and BioBB” at the BioExcel Summer School 2021	30
07/06/2021 - 11/06/2021	Presentation at CECAM Flagship Workshop: Open Databases Integration for Materials Design	
06/09/2021 - 09/09/2021	Keynote at the German Conference on Bioinformatics GCB 2021	250
20/09/2021	Invited talk at the FAIReScience workshop collocated at IEEE eScience conference	
09/11/2021	Presentation - “Computational Workflows as FAIR Digital Objects using RO-Crate” at “FAIR Digital Objects” plenary breakout at Research Data Alliance 18th Plenary	43
08/11/2021 - 12/11/2021	Hackathon projects on RO-Crate, WorkflowHub, GA4GH, RDMKit, and Bioschemas at ELIXIR BioHackathon Europe 2021	
15/11/2021	Invited talk - “FAIR Computational Workflows” at WORKS21: 16th Workshop on Workflows in Support of Large-Scale Science at Supercomputing 21	
22/11/2021	Presentations and hands-on exercises on BioBB at BioExcel course: Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel Building Blocks	12
28/02/2022 - 04/03/2022	2022 CWL Conference	
14/03/2022 - 15/03/2022	Hands-on exercises using BioBB at the PATC Course: Introduction to Simulation Environments for Life Sciences 2022	14
28/03/2022 - 03/04/2022	Lectures - “BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB)”, “Computational biomolecular simulation workflows using BioBB”, Tutorial - “Protein-Complex MD Setup with Jupyter Notebooks and BioBB” at the BioExcel School 2022	30
04/04/2022 - 07/04/2022	Software Sustainability Institute Collaborations Workshop 2022	60
26/04/2022	BioExcel Webinar 64: BioExcel HPC Workflows: predictive power and its applications in pharmacology (Presentation of Use Case 3 work)	35
31/05/2022 - 02/06/2022	Keynote, Lecture - “Biomolecular simulation workflows - the Bioexcel approach”, Presentations and hands on sessions - “Molecular dynamics	

	simulation”, “DNA shape analyses and protein-dna interaction” at CECAM workshop: Integrative approach to the theoretical study of chromatin	
13/06/2022 - 17/06/2022	Lectures - “BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB)”, “Computational biomolecular simulation workflows using BioBB”, Tutorial - “Protein-Complex MD Setup with Jupyter Notebooks and BioBB” at the BioExcel Summer School 2022	30
Total number of community member participations:		4215

Table 10: workflow tools & standards community events participated in during PM19-PM42, with number of confirmed participants where known.

Table 11 below shows a summary of recordings of lectures, demonstrations, presentations, and editions of the BioExcel webinar series relevant to the workflow tools and standards community hosted by [our YouTube channel](#) as well as by others, and the views these recordings accrued during the period PM19-PM42 - regardless of whether they were published during that period, or prior. In total such recordings accrued over 2600 views during the period.

Recording	Published	Views accrued during PM19 - PM42
CECAM COVID-19 webinar: HPC and Big Data Approaches in COVID-19 Research	PM17	1223
BioExcel Building Blocks - Part I (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	318
BioExcel Building Blocks - Part 2 (BioExcel Summer School 2020)	PM18	177
CECAM “The importance of being H.P.C. Earnest” webinar: “BioExcel Building Blocks and HPC: a Test Case in CoVID Research” , hosted by CECAM	PM19	417
Presentation on BioExcel, PyCOMPSs and ML - “Dislib: parallelizing machine learning and its application to scientific applications” at Advances in computational modelling of cellular processes and high-performance computing, 19th European Conference on Computational Biology	PM19	75
BioExcel Webinar #48: Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks	PM21	602
Using GROMACS and pmx with the BioExcel Building Blocks library to tackle COVID-19 research (BioExcel Winter School 2020)	PM24	364

9th Fenix Infrastructure webinar: Using ICEI resources for Atomistic Molecular Dynamics simulations , hosted by the Human Brain Project	PM26	277
Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel Building Blocks - Part 1 (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	262
Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel Building Blocks - Part 2 (BioExcel Summer School 2021)	PM30	170
BioExcel Webinar #64: BioExcel HPC Workflows: predictive power and its applications in pharmacology	PM40	250
Total views:		2635

Table 11: recordings relevant to the workflow tools & standards community available via the BioExcel and other YouTube channels, and the number of views they accrued during PM19-PM42.

BioExcel has been very active in participation in the workflow tools and standards community during the second phase of the BioExcel-2 project. In particular, the BioBB library and its associated demonstration workflows have been presented in more than 10 training events. BioBB was included in the BioExcel flagship schools (Summer, Winter, Spring), being presented together with our key applications (GROMACS, HADDOCK, pmx, CP2K) in a week-long school. It was also presented in MD-focused workflows (CSC Advanced GROMACS workshops 2021 and 2022, PRACE PATC Introduction to simulation environments for Life Sciences, 2019 to 2022, yearly) and multiscale simulation workflows (Integrative approach to the theoretical study of chromatin, CECAM). Besides, the special BioBB Virtual Training run in 2019 was also converted to a yearly event, and was extended from 2 to 3 days, adding a new section on HPC workflows, after analysing the feedback of the first edition. These events, each run for two hours (+1h if needed) on 3 days during one week, allowed us to show the power of the BioBB library in detail, and also allowed the attendees to work on some exercises in the days in between, which improved the level of learning and engagement from the participants. Finally, the library was also presented in a special industrial workshop with AstraZeneca (AZ) pharmaceutical company, together with the pmx code. This is reported in more detail in the ‘Industry’ section below.

Feedback received in all training was in general very good. Excluding the 3-day Virtual Training sessions, which gave us more time to dig into the BioBB library, a common output from the participants is that they would want to know more about the whole BioBB ecosystem, such as how to use it in HPC resources. An interesting outcome from some of the training events, in particular the BioExcel Schools, was a building block “wish list” - a list of potentially useful but missing building blocks in the library, assembled from the participants during the course. This is very important for us as it is helping to give priorities to our development plans towards the users’ needs. A particular assumption taken from the AZ workshop was that these companies usually want full control of the software they are using. They liked the full idea behind the library, but they could not wait for new building

blocks to be implemented, so they were thinking about whether coding their own building blocks was worth the effort. In general, the training events have been a very good way to engage with our community, and the impact is already noticeable in our development roadmap.

The second period of BioExcel-2 has been also dedicated to the exposition of the power of our BioExcel HPC workflows to the community. We started with a demo video that we shared with our closer friends in the community (*BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB) pre-exascale workflows video tutorial –COVID-19 example-*), with a demo on how to use our HPC workflows on the BSC Marenostrum 4 supercomputer, using an example based on COVID-19 research. These workflows were further presented in a CECAM “*The importance of being H.P.C. Earnest*”, webinar, in a talk titled “*BioExcel Building Blocks and HPC. A test case in COVID research*”. They were also presented as a success story for the ICEI/FENIX infrastructure, with the 9th Fenix Infrastructure Webinar “*Using ICEI resources for Atomistic Molecular Dynamics simulations*”, and the blog entry “*Using ICEI resources for Atomistic Molecular Dynamics simulations on COVID-19 related research*”. All talks were given by Prof. Modesto Orozco. Besides, a summary of the predictive power of the BioExcel pre-exascale workflows was presented in the BioExcel Webinar series: “*BioExcel HPC Workflows: predictive power and its applications in pharmacology*”, by Adam Hospital, Milosz Wieczór and Federica Battistini. Given the good results obtained using one of these pre-exascale workflows used for the prediction of resistance/sensitivity patterns to approved drugs for the Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) kinase domain variants, it is now being explored by Nostrum BioDiscovery (NBD) for potential application to other systems of interest.

In-depth Support

In the second period of BioExcel-2, support for BioBB users has continued to be primarily done by direct e-mails and through submission of GitHub issues. Questions in the AskBioExcel forum have been still scarce, with most of them coming usually after completion of training events. Questions from entry-level users have decreased in the MDWeb section of the AskBioExcel forum. However, the number of active MDWeb users is still high and sustained. This pushed us to develop the new [BioBB-Wfs](#) website, which replicates and updates some of the functionalities offered by the old [MDWeb](#) server.

Standards and Best Practice

The BioBB library from BioExcel has continued to push for best practices in FAIR software development, by the following extensions. Findability: registering all the demonstration workflows with global, unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers (with different flavours such as Jupyter Notebooks, Pure Python, Galaxy or CWL) in the WorkflowsHub platform; and Accessibility: with the special [biobb.usegalaxy.es](#) BioBB Galaxy instance and the new REST API programmatic interface ([BioBB-API](#)) and the new web-based GUI ([BioBB-Wfs](#)). A best practice

guide on using CWL workflows in HPC resources is being built. The expertise gained with our tests during the last year of BioExcel-2 is going to be summarised and will serve for both the CWL community (driving the development process from missing functionalities or issues found) and the biomolecular simulation community (how to build and launch CWL workflows in supercomputers).

On the standards side, BioExcel contributed to the definition of the [Biomolecular simulation data domain](#) of the ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit (RDMKit), an online guide containing good data management practices applicable to research projects. The website was populated with information on common data formats in the field and recommendations on what and how to store and share data from biomolecular simulations. UNIMAN has an integral part of the editorial leadership of RDMkit, which is now being expanded by other EOSC projects.

Besides, a face-to-face meeting was held with the [ELIXIR Data Stewardship Wizard](#) (DSW) team, a wizard designed to help researchers in the process of creation of Data Management Plans (DMPs). In the meeting, feedback from BioExcel (representing the biomolecular simulation community) was collected by the DSW developers, such as missing important information (or links to information), sections too biased to other fields, or links between the RDMKit and the DSW.

The [Bioschemas community](#) has become well established with regular contributions from a wide user base. We have contributed new profiles for [Computational workflows](#) and improved the profile for [Computational tools](#). This semantic markup is based on existing Linked Data standards and Bioschemas has grown in its adaption. Most recent improvements include tools for validation and consumption of Bioschemas markup.

We have continued our collaboration within the [BioCompute Object](#) (BCO) community which published the [IEEE 2791-2020 standard](#), helping BCO establish governance structures and a technical steering committee where UNIMAN is a member. ELIXIR partners have recently integrated BCO into the Galaxy workflow, which is also used by BioBB.

In the [Common Workflow Language](#) (CWL) we have been part of the leadership team and helped establish governance and transitioning the community to legally form part of the [Software Freedom Conservancy](#). We have contributed to the CWL community paper [<https://doi.org/10.1145/3486897>] which highlights the motivation for developing a standard for computational workflows. CWL continues to attract industry attention and new implementations, and in BioExcel is used heavily by BioBB workflows (see deliverables D2.6 [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5824544>] and D2.7).

Our collaboration on using RO-Crate together with Computational Workflows is exemplified in the [WorkflowHub](#) registry, which started as a BioExcel prototype, now developed and used by several EOSC projects including [EOSC-Life](#) and [BY-COVID](#).

More wider, we have helped establish the [Workflows Community Initiative](#) (WCI) with [leadership representation](#) by BSC and UNIMAN. As part of this collaboration across HPC workflow engine developers, users and researchers, we have formalised the [FAIR Computational Workflow](#) community as a working group. Following on from the initial [WCI Summits](#) where BioExcel participated and presented, WCI will now organise further events, webinars and newsletters to further broaden this community.

A broader aspect of workflows is considering any research software as FAIR objects, themselves needing rich descriptions, attributions, licensing, etc. This has been the focus of the Research Data Alliance (RDA)'s [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) Working group](#), where UNIMAN has contributed, culminating in the FAIR Principles for Research Software [<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>]. Further work on FAIR Research Software is starting in the recently started [FAIR-IMPACT](#) where EMBL-EBI and UNIMAN are participants.

We have contributed regularly to the activities of Global Alliance for Genomics and Health ([GA4GH](#)) activities, particularly for workflow execution standards WES/TES/TRS, described in a recent community paper [<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100029>]. GA4GH standards are strongly used by ELIXIR, WorkflowHub and Galaxy.

New EOSC projects starting in 2021/2022 with BioExcel partners and use of the standards mentioned above include [BY-COVID](#), [BioDT](#) (biodiversity), [EOSC4Cancer](#), Biodiversity Genomics Europe, AgroServe (plant science), [FAIR-IMPACT](#) (semantic artefacts), EuroScienceGateways (distributed workflow architecture). The fact that BioExcel's work on these standards have broadened out into such a diverse set of research domains shows their strength and generalizability.

A new collaboration has also been established recently between BioExcel and the Open Databases Integration for Materials Design ([OPTIMADE](#)) consortium. OPTIMADE was built with the aim of making materials databases interoperable by developing a fiction for a common REST API. The specification, focused on the Materials Sciences, already contained MD simulations, but were not compatible with the Life Sciences simulations. After direct discussions with BioExcel, an agreement was made to use our BioExcel-CV19 MD simulations database and its associated REST API to work together and try to improve and modify the OPTIMADE specification to include our simulations. The project is ongoing, with official pull requests proposals of biological data integration in the OPTIMADE specification [main repository](#).

User & Community Needs Analysis and Feedback

All the events where the BioBB library was presented were followed by a short survey. The value of the course and the expectations met for BioBB workshops were rated with an average of 4.5 over 5 (PATC surveys). For the BioExcel schools the rate was similar, but we were able to obtain more specific comments that will

help us a lot in the near future. We received very dissimilar notes, in a way corroborating that the library we are developing is not suited for all users. For example, in the BioExcel School on Biomolecular Simulations in March 2022, we received this comment:

“I have really enjoyed the workshop. If I may, I would like to suggest to use the BioExcel Building Blocks for all tutorial sessions if possible, as they make it a lot easier to follow each step without worrying to miss something or get stuck.”

But in the same survey, we also received this response for the “*What was the worst part of the workshop?*” question:

“If I had to choose an area it would be the BioExcel Building blocks, this confused me the most and I don't feel as if it was explained clearly. I feel that if more time could have been allocated to the BioBB tutorial, this would have helped.”

These comments help us in keeping with the hard work, and with trying to improve the training material and thinking about the proper time needed for the sessions and how to run them.

In general, Jupyter Notebooks were greatly appreciated in the training events. The possibility to interactively play with the workflow with the notebook cells and the integrated plots and macromolecule 3D visualizers make the process less boring and more impressive. And the combination of these notebooks and the BioExcel myBinder platform, which avoids any kind of installation process, is even more appreciated. We as teachers can go straight to the action, and our participants can learn from the very first minute about what they are interested in: the science behind the technology. Participants of the Virtual Training events organised with this infrastructure were very happy, and this was reflected in the surveys. Apart from that, surveys still denote a poor knowledge of workflow managers other than Galaxy or Nextflow in our field. In particular, CWL and HPC-focused workflow managers such as PyCOMPSs are still unfamiliar in the biomolecular simulation field, something we would need to improve in the coming years.

Industry

In D3.4 we reported that as a result of feedback from a Focus Group meeting for a number of SMEs at the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre in 2019 we developed a 2+ year strategy on what BioExcel will be for industrial users. This strategy prioritised the following three key elements: (1) Prepare and establish BioExcel Enterprises, (2) consolidate existing and establish new business opportunities, and (3) further define and validate the BioExcel value proposition.

During the second half of the project and in relation to (1), we are pleased to report that BioExcel Enterprises has been registered as a non-profit, members-led organisation to facilitate collaborative and commercial work for its members and the wider computational Life Science communities, including industry. Regarding (2) and (3) we have developed a business engagement framework based on the

experience we have gained from pilot projects with large pharma and SMEs. Much of this is described in D5.7 which provides a more business-focused, but complementary, perspective to the three key elements defined above. Our experience suggests that SMEs and organisations which do not have access to commercial software offer the biggest opportunity for support on a commercial basis.

Through the pilot projects with industry, we have built some strong relationships and herein we describe the results and in-depth support provided to Iktos, a US-based biotechnology company and AstraZeneca (AZ). We share the results and insights gathered from the surveys conducted following the provision of support and how these have and could influence the work of BioExcel going forward.

Community Participation

BioExcel (co-)organised and participated in a number of events in which we engaged with and/or supported around 216 members of the industry community, including both current and potential future users of all BioExcel core codes: GROMACS, PMX, HADDOCK, CP2K - as shown in **Table 12**.

Date	Event and participation	Participants
13/10/2020	AstraZeneca virtual training (session 1)	12
22/10/2020	AstraZeneca virtual training (session 2)	15
15/12/2020	Iktos virtual training on free energy calculations	9
26/01/2021	Iktos virtual training on free energy methods applications	12
25/02/2021 - 25/03/2021	Cecam: Simulation of open systems in Chemistry, Pharma, Food Science and Immuno-diagnostics: Rare-event methods at constant chemical potentials including constant pH - an E-CAM Industry Scoping Work	
12/04/2021 - 13/04/2021	Presentation at CROP-IB 2021 Breakthroughs in technology development, vegetable trait and crop improvement	150
23/05/2021	CSW Spring 2021 - HiPEAC - Industrial Challenges and Innovation Opportunities of CoEs in Medical/Bio/Pharma sectors. Recording available on YouTube (#CSWSpring21 / Industrial Challenges and Innovation Opportunities of CoEs in Medical/Bio/Pharma - YouTube , 134 views by PM42).	45
08/11/2021	Presentation on PMX at AbbVie Computer-Aided Drug Design seminar	30
28/06/2022 - 29/06/2022	Presentation at EBI-EMBL Industry workshop: AI/ML for Biologics and Protein Evolutionary Modelling	150
Total number of community member participations:		378

Table 12: industry community events participated in during PM19-PM42 with number of confirmed participants where known.

Our planned industry-specific event in 2021 at one of the main continental hubs for research in the pharmaceutical and biotech industry, e.g. Basel (CH) or Boston (US), did not go ahead due to the travel restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic.

In-depth Support

Iktos pilot

In D3.4 we reported that following the distribution of BioExcel brochures by Focus CoE at the BioFIT conference in December 2019, two SMEs offering virtual hit-to-lead discovery had contacted the WP5 team for support. Having followed these leads one in particular was looking promising to become the first in-depth support industry pilot for BioExcel.

A collaboration involving BioExcel partners KTH, IRB, UEDIN, NC and NBD was established with Iktos (iktos.ai), a company specialised in the development of artificial intelligence (AI) solutions applied to chemical research and drug design. Iktos expressed an interest in the Molecular Dynamics expertise offered through the CoE and following a series of discussions we defined a pilot which consisted of (i) provision of training in the use of GROMACS/pmx for advanced free energy calculations and (ii) a short-term PoC study to compare the results obtained using the fast-growth TI vs MM-GBSA methodologies. The latter was in line with Iktos' wish to understand whether advanced RBEF calculations offered an advantage over the computationally cheaper MM-GBSA free energy methods being used as part of their structure-based generative AI models. Thus, three milestones were defined in the RFP:

- Milestone #1: Fast-Growth TI relative ligand- binding free energy estimates for a test set of 10-15 ligands performs better than baseline MMGBSA calculations, quantified by Kendall rank correlation coefficient criterion $t_{FE} < -0.4$.
- Milestone #2: Workflow optimisation and variation in compute time allow relative ligand- binding free energy estimates for the test set with Kendall rank correlation coefficients at least up to $t_{FE} < -0.8$, in turn allowing to report an estimate on compute-time that is needed to reach a specified accuracy for the test set.
- Milestone #3: Relative ligand-binding free energy estimate workflow scales up to 100 compounds and performs better than baseline MMGBSA calculations.

Preliminary work focused on: (1) identifying a suitable target and associated ligands for which experimental and computational data was readily available, and (2) developing and testing a workflow for advanced protein-ligand relative free energy calculations using GROMACS/pmx.

(1) Up to five different targets were considered for the collaboration. In order to maximise the chance of success, the choice of target was ultimately based on a set of 'must' and 'nice to' have criteria, some of which are highlighted. From a computational perspective, small proteins without coordinated metal ions were

prioritised. Prior expertise with the target was also desirable. Experimentally generated structures in complex with ligands for which binding data was available was key.

(2) The workflow was based on the work by [Gapsys et al., 2020](#) which demonstrated that the non-equilibrium alchemy method can be used for large scale calculation of relative protein-ligand binding free energies. Part of the focus of this collaboration was to develop a workflow for protein-ligand binding free energy calculation which could be deployed on diverse HPC infrastructures. The first step in the protocol consists of ligand parameterization with the General Amber Force Field (GAFF) with ACPYPE ([Sousa da Silva and Vranken, 2012](#)). In step two, the entire set of molecules to be studied must be paired in order to calculate the relative binding energies for each pair of ligands. This is done by creating a connectivity map between all the studied set of molecules using LOMAP ([Liu et al., 2013](#)). In step three, pmx ([Gapsys et al., 2015](#)) is used to create the hybrid topology of each pair of molecules and all the systems have to be assembled, water molecules must be added to the simulation boxes and compensated for the extra charges with Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions. This can easily be done in a Python environment using Jupyter Notebook's interface where each step is sequentially automated. In step four, all the files needed for the MD simulations with GROMACS (2020.2) ([Spoel et al., 2005](#)) are created and the simulations are executed on HPC systems using a Makefile script with one simple command.

A retrospective study of the JNK1, with 21 ligands, and PTP1B, with 23 ligands, systems described in the [Wang et al. \(2015\)](#) database was performed during protocol development. A number of tests were carried out during which different combinations of the number of non-equilibrium transitions and the simulation lengths were varied. In summary, and considering the computational cost involved and the reproducibility of the results, 2ns equilibrium simulations and 30 non-equilibrium transitions of 50ps each was chosen as the method to use in the workflow. The final workflow to calculate the relative binding free energy starts with an energy minimization followed by 10 ps of NVT simulation and a 2 ns equilibrium simulation for each state in the thermodynamic cycle. Following this, 30 snapshots are extracted from each simulation in equilibrium and used as starting points for the 50ps non-equilibrium simulations described above and finally pmx is used to calculate the relative free binding energy (ΔG) of each transition. Calculations are performed in triplicate for each pair of ligands. The results (**Figure 6**) demonstrate good Pearson correlation and τ -Kendall coefficients and reasonably good MUE and RMSE (lower than ~1.5 kcal/mol) values. Furthermore, the workflow is computationally cheaper (42ns total computation time per ligand pair versus 240ns) and uses one force field (GAFF) compared with two force fields (GAFF and CHARMM) as described in the original publication previously mentioned.

Figure 6: Results for the JNK1 and PTP1B systems were obtained using the CGI method. The best replicate for each pair of ligands was selected for representation.

Once the workflow was optimised and validated using the JNK1 and PTP1B benchmark systems, a Github repository was created to store all the files needed and to facilitate its usability. With a Jupyter Notebook's interface in a Python environment, the setup of each system can be done easily and sequentially.

Work on the Iktos target of choice was initiated using a test set of 14 ligands belonging to the same series. The test set contained enough chemical diversity that it was only possible to connect 11 ligands above a previously established LOMAP threshold. This highlights one of the limitations of using this methodology, i.e. ligand pairs should share high similarity and, in particular in relation to any present alicyclic rings. For these 11 ligands, it was possible to calculate the relative binding free energy and obtain a Pearson correlation of -0.63 and a τ -Kendall coefficient of -0.60 (**Figure 7**). Removal of the outlier (red dot in **Figure 7**) improved the Pearson correlation to -0.77 and τ -Kendall coefficient to -0.69. Two different MM-GBSA calculation approaches were used to compare MM-GBSA calculations and the TI-RBFE method. For both MM-GBSA methods the obtained Pearson correlation were -0.26 and -0.60, and the τ -Kendall coefficients were -0.18 and -0.40 respectively.

Figure 7: Results for the Iktos protein kinase test set, where 11 ligands could be connected and there is one outlier (red dot). The best results were obtained using the BAR method and selecting the best replicate for each pair of ligands.

Based on these results and the work that had already been invested in optimisation of the workflow using the JNK1 and PTP1B systems, it was agreed that Milestones #1 and #2 had been achieved and the efforts should move towards reaching Milestone #3.

Before running the workflow with a full batch of 100 ligands, a small subset of 11 ligands with similar chemistries was extracted from the batch. The purpose of this was two-fold; firstly, to test if two different partners (Iktos and NBD) could reproduce the results whilst running on two different HPC facilities (GENCI and CIRRUS respectively) and secondly to see if any issues were encountered when running the workflow on selected ligands with similar chemistries. The results are presented below (**Figure 8**) and show a Pearson correlation of -0.50 and -0.58 respectively, and a τ -Kendall coefficient of -0.49 for this subset of 11 ligands can be achieved at both HPC facilities, proving the reproducibility of the workflow on different HPC systems.

Figure 8: Results the subset of 11 ligands obtained from simulations performed at GENCI HPC and from CIRRUS HPC. Results calculated using the BAR method and selecting the best replicate for each pair of ligands.

Based on these results, the workflow was applied to the full batch of 100 ligands. Only 61 ligands displayed sufficiently high connectivity and the results achieved for these are shown in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9: Results for the batch with 100 ligands, where 61 ligands could be connected. The best results were obtained using the BAR method and selecting the best replicate for each pair of ligands.

Both the Pearson and τ -Kendall correlation coefficients are lower than desired. This can be explained because of the broader diversity in the ligands from the larger batch. Working with larger batches of ligands poses more challenges and it is likely more critical to select ligands with a higher degree of similarity, especially around the conservation of alicyclic rings. Further studies are clearly needed to improve the results with such a large dataset of molecules to obtain better Pearson correlation and τ -Kendall coefficient.

US-based biotechnology company pilot

Another pilot project was with a US-based biotechnology company. This client company insisted on being anonymous to meet their confidentiality policies. They required support for software installation, remote training on PMX and single use-case limited to public datasets. Three different milestones were defined in the Request for Proposal:

1. Installation and validation on a local workstation at the client company (anonymised due to confidentiality restrictions)
2. Performance optimisation and training for GROMACS and PMX
3. Free energy calculations for a target protein receptor interaction region (unable to specify due to confidentiality).

Several mutations from a publication (unable to disclose due to confidentiality), of experimental free energy data, were selected to calculate the free energy with GROMACS and PMX, in the local computers of the client company. BioExcel Partner, Nostrum Biodiscovery (NBD), will support the client with any issues they have during execution of free energy calculations on their workstation.

Before the start of milestone 3, NBD performed different calculations to gather enough information to fulfil some inquiries of the client company users in charge of running a maximum of 30 mutations for milestone 3. Firstly, the influence of the initial conformations of mutated residues on the software was studied. Rosetta, FoldX and PMX were used to generate two different mutants. Next, TI simulations were conducted with GROMACS/PMX and free energies were estimated and compared with the different approaches used to generate starting structures. It was possible to observe that the utilisation of different software for the preparation of initial structures of mutants does not have a significant impact on the results. Then, the effect of the selected force field and the average of the results with the different force fields was studied. Amber14, amber99 and charmm36 were used in the different simulations to calculate the free energy for two different mutations. It was possible to conclude that averaging of the results using amber99 and charmm36 provides the best results.

The next step was to study the variability of the free energy estimations, analysing the results obtained with two different protocols: the original protocol and a more expensive protocol with a longer equilibrium simulation time and a higher number of transitions. The results suggested that increasing simulation lengths and number of transitions did not improve results. Finally, the feasibility of estimating the free energy of charge-changing mutations was studied with two different mutations that change the global charge of the system. That point is still

under study and soon we will obtain further insights that will allow us to determine the degree of accuracy when applying charge-changing mutations. While waiting for the charge-changing mutations results, the mutations that do not imply any change of the global charge of the system can start to be studied by the client company and BioExcel partners will help them to resolve any issue or doubt they might encounter.

AstraZeneca pilot

Following discussions between BioExcel partner NC and AZ an agreement was reached to hold a face-to-face AZ-BioExcel workshop focused on the use of GROMACS/pmx and their application to specific use cases. The main aim of the workshop would be to deliver concrete options for collaboration between BioExcel and AZ scientists. As a prelude to the workshop, a virtual training event focused on Molecular Dynamics and advanced free energy calculations using GROMACS/pmx and workflows using BioExcel building blocks was held over two sessions. To set expectations, a flyer was prepared for the training event and this is included in Appendix 3 for reference. Surveys were conducted after each session and the results are presented in the relevant section below.

MPG has further worked with the AZ scientists in incorporating the non-equilibrium free energy calculation protocol into the workflow management system Icolos (<https://github.com/MolecularAI/Icolos>) developed at AZ. The collaboration continues with an aim to develop a prototype use case where commercial and open-source software can be used interchangeably in a unified workflow to obtain accurate protein-ligand binding affinity estimates.

Best Practice

MPG has contributed to the best practice guide for constructing, preparing, and evaluating protein-ligand binding affinity benchmarks. Currently, the guide is readily accessible on a pre-print server (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.06222>) and in the future will be published in the LiveCoMS journal (Living Journal of Computational Molecular Science).

User & Community Needs Analysis and Feedback

Iktos virtual training survey

As part of the collaboration with Iktos training in the use of GROMACS/pmx for advanced free energy calculations was provided. The training was delivered virtually over two 2h sessions on separate days. Session 1 covered the theory behind free energy perturbation methods and was attended by 9 participants. Session 2 covered the theory behind setting up a pipeline for relative ligand-binding free energy calculations using GROMACS/pmx and was attended by 12 participants. We conducted an online post-training survey after session 2 to gather feedback for both sessions, which was completed by 6 participants who had attended both sessions. 100% of survey respondents rated the training as Excellent or Very Good, with general feedback from two participants stating that: *“I found the training informative and very clear”* and *“The background of the problem was presented very clearly. The questions were answered in detail”*.

When asked specifically about what the best part of the training was, a number of participants mentioned the introduction to different methods of free energy perturbation (FEP) and the clarity with which these were presented. Regarding the worst part of the training, responses were more varied, e.g. *“I don't think there was any particular bad part. Simulation setup seemed a little less prepared, and the format could I think be improved to allow one to grasp more practical knowledge”* and *“the lack of time to tackle absolute binding free energy calculations”*.

100% of respondents stated that their learning objectives had been achieved as a result of the training and the majority (5 out of 6) said that they will continue to use or start to (re-)use GROMACS as a result of the training. When asked about what additional training or support they would like, most stated that a practical session and/or additional practical examples would be desirable.

US-based SME virtual training survey

Two scientists received the training and one completed the survey (also involved in the installation). That person rated the training as very good. Each session was followed immediately up by an informal interview with the pilot coordinator who received much positive feedback, consistent with the survey responses.

Improvers from the survey and interviews included:

- “Complex software - it needs a lot of support to get it to work”
- “Difficulty with finding the most recent installation documentation - this should be easier to find. Too much old documentation available caused confusion.”
- A desire for more on “Use of tools to further automate calculations”.

It was noted that this client preferred interviews over surveys. This possibility will be accommodated in future as necessary, using a more structured approach to the interview(s) which will be aligned to the survey questions.

AstraZeneca virtual training output

Session 1 was attended by 12 participants of which 8 completed the online post-training survey. 75% of survey respondents rated the training as Excellent or Very Good, with general feedback from one participant stating that: *“Very informative and engaging lectures and valuable tutorial”*.

When asked specifically about what the best part of the training was, most participants mentioned the theoretical background provided in the lectures. Regarding the worst part of the training, responses were more varied but of particular interest was feedback related to applicability in drug discovery, i.e. *“There was not so much focus on streamlining and automation which would help apply the applications to day-to-day project work”*. In relation to this comment, when participants were asked if they use or have used GROMACS, 7 out of 8 responded that they did, but one specifically stated that they do not use it anymore because they had *“access to more integrated comp. chem. licensed softwares”*. Counter to this, one participant mentioned that *“I have always used GROMACS and I always will. Actually, thanks to this workshop I have discovered new features that*

I can't wait to use". Regarding the use of pmx, none of the participants had used it before. With regards to the use of pmx the responses were mixed, with the majority falling within the category of being 'curious' or 'under investigation' or 'not knowing' whether they will use it going forward.

75% of respondents stated that their learning objectives had been achieved as a result of the training, with the other 25% stating that this was done only partially. When asked about what additional training or support they would like, the responses were varied but included support and automation around absolute binding free energy calculation, system preparation and molecule parametrisation. Most of the feedback aligned with what was captured during the post-training discussions described below.

Session 2 was attended by 15 participants of which 6 completed the online post-training survey. 83% of survey respondents rated the training as Excellent or Very Good, with a couple of participants stating that: *"...I appreciated getting a flavour of the building blocks available"* and *"thanks for the training, it was interesting and looks like great libraries. I will definitely give it a try next time I need to touch GROMACS"*.

When asked specifically about what the best part of the training was, half of respondents mentioned the introduction provided during this session, i.e. 'getting to know about the BioExcel project, its philosophy and goals'. One participant specifically mentioned *"being able to interactively follow the workflows step-by-step"*. Regarding the worst part of the training, a couple of respondents mentioned that the session was *"...rather packed, might have benefitted from splitting over two days"* and *"It was a little long for me, I think the command line version could have been skipped since it is essentially the same calls in a loop... Maybe instead a few slides saying that can of course script these calls and a few pointers about it would have sufficed"*.

We received feedback on which molecular modelling tasks should be automated using workflows and which building blocks would be most useful in daily work. Although responses were different, some had similar themes. Here we highlight two examples which capture the essence of this: *"Set-up blocks, (pmx-based) free energy ones, analysis blocks"*, *"Prof. John Chodera has a slide that captures it: Automate. Everything"*. Participants were asked what the biggest challenges they face with respect to developing their own workflows with the main reason being 'time' to do so. Preparation of MD systems, scaling to 100k+ ligand libraries and quality of output were also mentioned. The importance of having a GUI as a key feature in the choice of a workflow manager/descriptor was probed. 67% of respondents said 'No' with one stating that: *"..actually I find GUIs tend to be hopeless for large scale work and lead to irreproducibility. However, 3D vis and inspection capacities are very important to me in order to understand what is actually happening in simulations, ... My overall feeling is that the 'usability' and 'robustness' of FEP tools is not at the stage where they are reliable for inclusion in high-throughput automated workflows"*.

83% of respondents stated that their learning objectives had been achieved as a result of the training. No reasons were provided by the individual who stated their training objectives had not been met. All respondents stated they would recommend the training to their colleagues. When asked about what additional training or support they would like, the responses were varied but mentioned “*how to do new blocks in practice*” and “*...some more examples of existing complex workflows, In particular end-to-end FEP workflows*”.

In a follow up collaboration, MPG with AstraZeneca teams incorporated the pmx based free energy calculation protocol for protein-ligand relative binding affinity calculation into the workflow management system Icolos developed by AstraZeneca’s Molecular AI department. Afterwards, a proof-of-concept study was carried out by performing the calculations to evaluate binding affinities with various combinations of modules in the workflow. It was successfully demonstrated that in such a workflow commercial software can be fully replaced by the open-source packages (manuscript in preparation).

Questions and discussions from each of the training sessions were captured electronically and after each session we had the opportunity to further probe participants based on these records. Based on this and the results of the post-training surveys we were able to get a very good understanding of the needs, opportunities and challenges faced by AZ’s computational scientists. **Table 13** highlights the top 4 opportunities for collaboration which were identified from a total of more than 20.

Session during which feedback was obtained	Priority	Opportunity	Comment and follow up
1 and 2	1	Develop a workflow for ensemble docking based on crystal structure and docked ligand poses, followed by Molecular Dynamics for validation and absolute free energy calculation. The accuracy would not have to be in the 1 kcal/mol range for dGs.	Current status on absolute free energy calculations using GROMACS/pmx described in publication (Gapsys et al. 2022), formed the basis for the establishment of a collaboration with AZ.
1	=2	Develop a workflow for calculating relative-binding free energies starting from ligand smile strings and including ligand parametrisation. The workflow should scale to +500 ligands.	Was currently not in the development plans but could be reviewed by MPG and IRB.
1	=2	Develop a demonstrator for how to run free energy calculations on proteins containing unnatural amino acids.	Was currently in the long-term plans for MPG.
1	3	Develop a free energy benchmark for RNA and RNA-based therapeutics.	Free energy calculations on RNA is currently implemented in pmx but is largely untested.

Table 13: Opportunities for collaboration between BioExcel and AZ.

In a similar fashion, discussions with UU at the 2019 *Gordon Conference on “Computational aspects of Biomolecular NMR”* highlighted some of the biological systems and drug modalities which pharma are working on currently and how our docking tool HADDOCK could be used in this context. Since then, we have seen more companies obtaining a HADDOCK licence, and have received positive feedback that some companies have done their internal benchmarking of antibody-antigen modelling tools and come to the conclusion HADDOCK performs best.

Key Opinion Leader (KOL) in-depth interviews

Background

Our mostly tactical approaches to understand the needs of users within the defined communities have served us well to shape our engagements and further develop our core software and associated training. With a view to obtaining a different perspective, we decided to take a more strategic approach to externally validate current project activities at a higher level and gather input to shape the future direction of BioExcel. For this we decided to conduct in-depth interviews with internal and external KOLs in the field of HPC and molecular modelling and simulation.

Preparation

To help define the topics and questions for the KOL interviews we held a well-attended (28 participants) internal workshop at our January 2021 all-hands meeting. During the workshop participants were asked to provide a forward-looking perspective by answering the following questions: (i) What is BioExcel good at?, (ii) How can BioExcel improve what it is already doing within its current scope and means?, (iii) Where do you see opportunities for BioExcel to expand its activities, e.g. new topic, new software, new community?, (iv) What should not be part of BioExcel in future? The responses were collated and fell within a series of categories as shown in **Figure 10**. Some categories were clearly associated, and this is represented by the overlapping circles. A number of responses were relevant to how the CoE currently operates and how this could be improved. These responses will be used to shape the future operation of the CoE but were not used to design the KOL interviews.

Figure 10: Categories and overlap. The numbers in red represent how many responses fell within a particular category, thus giving an indication of importance.

The questions for the KOL interviews were structured into five parts, some of which were aligned to the six objectives of the CoE. The full list of questions is provided in Appendix 3. Briefly:

- PART 0 was about obtaining further background and insights into the KOL being interviewed and their use and access to computing infrastructure.
- PART 1, aligned to the BioExcel CoE Objectives 1 (world-leading software) & 2 (Convergence of HPC/HPDA and usability), and was about building a better understanding of the current challenges in reaching exascale computing, the areas of life science where exascale computing will be important and how this can be showcased.
- PART 2, aligned to BioExcel CoE Objective 3 (User-driven development), and was about identifying grand challenges of scientific and industrial importance to current and future users of BioExcel-supported codes.
- PART 3, aligned to BioExcel CoE Objectives 4 (addressing the skill gap), 5 (effective dissemination), 6 (CoE sustainability), and covered user engagement and provision of end-to-end support for users.
- PART 4 provided an opportunity to interviewees to provide additional insights on the topics covered and ask further questions.

Execution

KOLs were contacted individually and requested to participate in the interviews. By way of introduction some background on the BioExcel CoE and the purpose of the interviews was provided by email. If the KOL agreed to be interviewed, additional information on the BioExcel CoE and which parts would be covered was provided. Not all parts of the interview were covered with each KOL. This was due to time constraints (all interviews were limited to one hour) and our desire to

focus on the questions and topics which were most relevant to each KOL. The interviews were conducted by at least two individuals from the CoE, with one of them having relevant expertise in the topics being discussed. This was important to ensure credibility with the KOLs and to enable us to ask relevant follow-up questions based on their answers. We conducted a series of five interviews with internal KOLs to test the interview format and the questions. This exercise was used in particular to refine and further expand some of the questions and to gather suggestions regarding which external KOLs to target. **Table 14** summarises some of the key information relevant to the KOLs interviewed.

Internal or External	KOL Background	Location	PARTs covered during interview
Internal	Academia. Professor. Head of Department. Study of biomolecules, interactions and drug design. Software development and services.	Netherlands	0, 1, 3 & 4
Internal	Academia. Professor. Head of Group. Physical chemistry, biomolecular systems and materials science.	Finland	0, 1, 2, 3 & 4
Internal	Academia. Head of Group. Workflows and distributed computing.	Spain	0, 1, 2 & 4
Internal	Academia. Professor. Head of Group. Computational and lab-based biophysics. Molecular Dynamics software development.	Sweden	0, 1, 2 & 4
Internal	Academia. Professor. Head of Department. Computer Science specialised in HPC. Molecular Dynamics, Fluid Dynamics, Materials Science, Climate.	Germany	0, 1, 3 & 4
External	Academia. Head of Group. Quantum Mechanics and Quantum Chemistry. Co-developer of Molecular Dynamics software package.	US (Florida)	0, 1, 2, 3 & 4
External	Academia. Head of Group. Computational Biology, Structural Bioinformatics. Developing, applying and disseminating integrative structural biology software and methods.	US (California)	0, 1, 3 & 4
External	Industry. Head of Department. Computational Chemistry. Ultra-High Throughput Virtual Screening, Machine Learning, Informatics.	Belgium	0, 1, 2 & 4
External	Industry. Head of Group. Quantum Mechanics. Computational Chemistry. Molecular Dynamics, Free Energy calculations.	UK	0, 1, 2 & 4

Table 14: KOLs summary.

Each interview was recorded, and responses were captured electronically. The audio files for each interview were reviewed in cases where electronic notes were incomplete or ambiguous. The raw data from each interview was analysed and actionable feedback and specific insights based on this were captured.

To help define the way forward based on the analysis of the KOL interviews we held an internal workshop at our September 2021 all-hands meeting, which was attended by 15 participants, some of which had been involved in the KOL interviews. Given the amount of actionable feedback to be discussed during the workshop participants were divided into two groups based on their background and expertise. Each group would focus on actionable feedback from two PARTs: PART 0 (usage and access to computing infrastructure) and PART 1 (reaching exascale), and PART 2 (user-driven development) and PART 3 (user engagement and support) respectively.

Results and way forward

Tables 15 to 18 provide a simplified summary of some of the actionable feedback, analysis (new insight and additional context supporting this) and proposed follow up from each PART of the KOL interviews conducted between March and July 2021. Actions which were already being followed up or had the potential to be followed up in the short term were ‘routed’ through BioExcel-2. Actions which felt longer term could be ‘routed’ through BioExcel-3 or BioExcel Enterprises.

Actionable feedback	New insight	Additional context	Resulting actions	Follow-up route
PART 0 - usage and access to computing infrastructure				
Almost all of the compute resources being used by both Academic and Industrial users (HPC clusters, Cloud, etc.) now have a lot of available performance in the form of dedicated GPU nodes.	Ability of BioExcel software to effectively use GPUs including scaling efficiently across multiple GPUs of various types should be prioritised.	Some BioExcel codes have some limitations in effective usage of modern GPU infrastructure	We should prioritise software development that uses GPUs effectively and scales efficiently across multiple GPUs	BioExcel-2
Users are actively using AWS infrastructure for their simulations (mostly industrial users). It would be good if software and workflows will be ready for deployment on AWS.	We should make ready-to-use workflows and setups for effective usage of BioExcel software on AWS infrastructure. Usual IT departments and support of companies are not working with the required (scientific) software stack on that kind of infrastructure	This is particularly important for companies, that prefer to use their own clusters or AWS for security reasons	Focus on providing portable, adaptable (composable) components, examples that can be adapted.	BioExcel Enterprises

Table 15: Summary of actionable feedback log from KOL interviews related to PART 0: usage and access to computing infrastructure.

Actionable feedback	New insight	Additional context	Resulting actions	Follow-up route
PART 1 - reaching exascale				
One of the possible ways to reach exascale is to do large-scale screening. By effectively splitting workflow into using many small weakly-coupled tasks or by using ensemble methods	Preparation of workflows showcase and for example large-scale FEP screening would be a good approach.	"golden dream" would be to use exascale machines to simulate whole or parts of the cell	Continue to develop workflow tools to enable this, and showcase calculations as an example of how to do this, in a way that is adaptable and usable by users.	BioExcel-2
Increasing usage of ML in data analysis and development of the new neural-network based force fields should be taken into account for further developments.	BioExcel(-3) should aim to incorporate and capitalise on ML expertise (application of ML techniques, software & hardware - e.g. ML-specific accelerators)	It is also a good field for contact with industry both hardware developers and users of our software	Investigate how use of output data from BioExcel codes can be used by ML packages and whether there are possible improvements.	BioExcel-3

Table 16: Summary of actionable feedback log from KOL interviews related to PART 1: reaching exascale.

Actionable feedback	New insight	Additional context	Resulting actions	Follow-up route
PART 2 - user-driven development: challenges and use cases				
BioExcel codes are not ready for non-expert users and work needed to package things up. BioExcel codes are more distinct for one task or another. Ultimately, BioExcel still has too many standalone tools not easily/optically configured for the applications that need to be run for.	BioExcel codes has too many standalone tools not easily/optically configured for the applications that need to be run for in drug discovery. Work needed to package things up for non-expert users and drug discovery applications.	Most people in the group have relatively shallow knowledge of a wide variety of tools. In-depth knowledge and expertise around particular codes is rare. For example, even with PMX - group is very familiar with it by now, but despite multiple training sessions, there are really not many people in the group who can easily run PMX. Take the BioExcel tools with clear identification of where strengths are, Janssen could give feedback to BioExcel on how they think a particular tool can best be used (or not!) to do particular things. - There is a commercial company that created wrappers around HADDOCK to fully run it	- Work with Janssen and other pharma companies on a plan to make BioExcel tools fit for the job to be done and competitive with commercial software - Work with industry to define big red button scenarios needed - Aim to provide a few scenarios where you can run with one command on the command line (big red button tasks). Likely highly specific to the infrastructure - Make the documentation more readable for non experts - Facilitate the process for dedicated external companies to create those wrappers - Gain Industry feedback early on development on HADDOCK 3 (and other codes)	BioExcel Enterprises
- Application of tools to solve or predict manufacturing challenges could be valuable. Polymorph detection is important for pharma. - Drug-delivery mechanisms such as lipid nanoparticle encapsulation could be one of the most important areas for the pharma industry.	BioExcel should place more emphasis on the use of its tools to address challenges faced by pharma in 1) drug-delivery and manufacturing and 2) polymorph detection	- Need additional expertise/partners in BioExcel-3 to address this, potentially in material science. Liquid nanoparticle especially important in (mRNA) vaccine delivery - crystal form of a compound very difficult to predict	- Follow up and validate the importance and potential impact - Define how large the system needs to be to address exascale use case	BioExcel-2

Table 17: Summary of actionable feedback log from KOL interviews related to PART 2: user-driven development, challenges and use cases.

Actionable feedback	New insight	Additional context	Resulting actions	Follow-up route
PART 3 - user engagement and support: provision of end-to-end support				
Support forums good but could include support for other software (eg AMBER and Charmm), and expand training to these codes also; There should be mixed training on different codes at same event i.e. GROMACS (mainly EU) and CHARMM and AMBER (mainly US).	Expand support and training to non BioExcel codes (e.g. CHARMM, AMBER).	Will help to expand beyond Europe at the same time We are EU-based and funded so should we expand to codes not embedded in the CoE? Tricky to split support if we don't have the partners (code-developer) onboard There is also NAMD/GAUSSIAN/etc to consider and specifically the FF for these codes so where does the support stop? When we respond to users around general best-practice type questions we also address relevant queries around other codes	Redirect questions to AMBER/CHARMM mailing lists - make the signposts clearer Highlight if we do joint training/webinars. Link to previous material. Show off AMBER BioBB workflow https://ask.bioexcel.eu/c/general-topics-in-molecular-dynamics/19	BioExcel-2
Could do more consultant level support on specific applications, e.g. give recommendations on what hardware to buy to run a particular code given a certain budget.. Can see opportunities for working with BioExcel experts on a 1-2 week consulting basis e.g. to get PMX running more robustly, higher throughput, running more cost-effectively		In conflict with a separate comment: More documentation and guides. Software scale. Better tutorials rather than having to hire new person per customer Not necessarily a conflict as support will be based on need and ability to pay for bespoke or specific support which could be carried out by BioExcel Enterprises	Identify common topics at generic level that are in scope for the BioExcel project. Dedicated consultancy is for BioExcel enterprise Need to work out how the 'flow' of requests is handled and to be met by BioExcel CoE or BioExcel Enterprises	BioExcel Enterprises

Table 18: Summary of actionable feedback log from KOL interviews related to PART 3: user engagement and support, provision of end-to-end support.

Conclusions from KOL interviews

- Overall, the KOL interviews worked well to gather useful insights for the future of BioExcel. Internal feedback received after the interviews had been carried out, suggested that these should have been started earlier and conducted on a regular basis during BioExcel-2.
- Some internal feedback suggested that some of the insights may not have been ‘new’ or provided new information, yet these insights had not been officially captured, discussed broadly and/or consciously acted upon. The proportionally higher number of internal KOL interviews carried out may well have contributed to the feeling that the insights were not particularly novel.
- A considerable amount of resources were involved in preparing for and conducting the interviews but having done this and defined a set of questions, a list of relevant potential KOLs to be contacted and a process for the interviews, it will be considerably easier and less time consuming to build on this exercise in future.
- The exercise provided additional value as it served to further build and strengthen our network and relationships in the field.
- The proposal is to continue conducting these on an ongoing basis, but we want to ensure we get maximum value from our invested effort by first ensuring that we follow through with the resulting actions which have been identified.

Appendix 1: Detailed feedback from HADDOCK web server survey

This appendix lists detailed feedback (free text responses) to the ongoing HADDOCK web server user survey recorded during the reporting period. The first section - “Evidence of impact from detailed HADDOCK web server user survey feedback” - lists positive feedback responses that confirm unambiguously the value of the work done in providing the new version 2.4 HADDOCK web server. The second section - “Detailed actionable feedback from HADDOCK web server user survey” - lists suggestions for improvements, which we have categorised and analysed to generate the higher-level aggregated prioritisation described in the main body of this document.

Evidence of impact from detailed HADDOCK web server user survey feedback

This section lists positive feedback responses that confirm unambiguously the value of the work done in providing the new version 2.4 HADDOCK web server

When asked for general comments regarding the new (version 2.4) HADDOCK web server, a number of users provided positive overall feedback that highlighted the value of HADDOCK’s functionality and availability as a web-based service:

- *Generates most reliable results and most user-friendly docking software I have used so far.*
- *Having HADDOCK online and freely accessible with all of the support forums make it very easy to use and I train students to use it in combination with their NMR or low resolution cryoEM, SAXS, etc. The support, openness, history, and efficiency of the server make it one of the best.*
- *This is a big help to my teams work. We appreciate y'all*
- *Wish Rosetta had a nice portal like this! Amazing work, y'all*
- *The tutorials are VERY helpful!*
- *I will recommend HADDOCK to my students*
- *Compared with the local version, the webserver is more convenient for my scientific research work, and the local version also allows me to explore more and use this software.*
- *I am new to Haddock, but found it very user friendly. Thank you.*
- *Very user friendly.*
- *I appreciate your work and looking forward to Simulation feature*
- *I am satisfied! Congratulations and thank you for making such great tools available!*
- *I like the whole process of docking. It is very easy to work with this portal.*
- *It is great*
- *I love using HADDOCK!*
- *I can't wait to compare your program to our previously determined RosettaDock complex! Thank you for making a user friendly portal which is much easier than Rosetta in my opinion.*
- *Great job!*
- *It's absolutely user friendly*

- *I am newish to docking and yours is the best portal out there. I love it!!!*
- *Thanks for making this public. For the researchers that do not have computational resources, it is very useful.*
- *All in all, I found the software very user friendly and tutorials are extremely knowledgeable.*
- *Great platform, thanks a lot for providing this!*
- *Thanks for making it possible to dock DNA to proteins*

When asked specifically about the usability / user friendliness of the web portal interface, a number of users provided positive feedback:

- *It's working excellent, keep it up*
- *It is already a well step-by-step procedure*
- *No suggestions, found the interface very user friendly*
- *I have no suggestion to improve relative to other web portals*
- *It is very poggers, don't have anything to suggest (yet) :)*
- *It has given me desired results*
- *It's perfect*
- *Pretty much everything is straightforward*
- *Nice work!*
- *Presently no issues*
- *It is great for me*
- *As someone who hasn't done docking at all until now, I found that I had to just familiarise myself with the web portal interface as one would normally have to when doing something for the first time. But once I got the hang of it and became more familiar with the terminology, it was quite easy and simple to use.*
- *It's already at its best*

When asked to clarify why they rated the new 2.4 version of the HADDOCK web portal compared to the previous 2.2 version in the way they did, users who had used both provided the following detailed feedback, confirming the impact of our work:

- *The previous interface was way more clouded and complicated, now at least the errors give a hint on what might have went wrong*
- *Definitely improved from previous version*
- *The old portal was definitely less clear, and compiling the program seemed easier.*
- *This interface is clear and concise.*
- *Seems much more user friendly and intuitive*
- *Selection of interacting pairs is easier; more options to set up the simulation*
- *I find 2.4 portal very user-friendly. It's easy to submit a job and get my results.*
- *Very nice auto-fill fields, visualization option of active/passive*
- *It is really easy to navigate through the software selecting the docking parameters.*
- *Great improvements*

- *In error happening situation, HADDOCK2.2 have to start all again when refreshing web site. But HADDOCK2.4 is separated into 3 parts and more easier to correct parameters*
- *I had some problems to convert pdb format to haddock format. However, now, thankfully, It converts automatically.*
- *The workspace is very useful. Furthermore, I like the fact that you receive error messages before your final submission :)*
- *The 2.4 portal provides the user with information about where uploads fail in a clear manner before proceeding to further steps. The new portal also provides information about what default parameters change if certain selections are made in a previous step.*
- *I only used the old system a few times, so I was really only learning. That being said, I found the new portal much easier to learn.*
- *2.4 gives me more specific error part of my input than 2.2*
- *I do enjoy the new layout and certainly the increased capacity of the new portal. Adding radius of gyration and symmetry restraints is useful for the system I am modelling with HADDOCK, even if the radius of gyration does not contribute significantly.*
- *The overview and the design is much better, like the tool for the active residue selection*
- *Just seems smoother and reports errors more obviously.*
- *This one is kinder, and it has explanations right there for what one should do*
- *I like it that in the easy mode more options are available. Also, the description of the input format has improved a lot.*
- *It is nice that specific parameters for the run are set up after choosing from the drop down menus.*
- *The options or arrays available for docking have enhanced significantly however the complexity of the process is enhanced in the process*
- *I'm very satisfied with the webportal, you did great work!*
- *I have not used the portal extensively, but probably will do so in the coming months/years. So far I'm very satisfied! Great work and thanks for making it so accessible!*
- *The submission segregation has allowed us to focus on specific things. It makes it more sleek and more comprehensible.*
- *One of the things that I had trouble with was that it was not clear what kind of link between the receptor and the ligand should be inserted.*
- *I think the new web portal gives excellent information on every single choice, which helps beginners like me to choose the right settings.*
- *It was easy to use, but I've never tried the 2.2 portal. I really like the simplicity of your interface.*
- *More user friendly*
- *Clearer error messages, visualization, feedback regarding upload files, direct interaction with inputs and parameters. Nice!*
- *User friendly interface*
- *Being able to review input parameters and their definitions accompanied by conceptual definitions helps users understand the coupling process*
- *It gives an exact information if an error is experienced and is user-friendly*

- *The interface is more attractive and user-friendly. Amazing work! Thank you.*
- *I love that I can visualize the models afterwards without needing to download them. It is very useful for me to screen things so quickly. I also love the features on the graphs that allow you to isolate certain clusters to look at.*
- *The use of the bootstrap plugin made the site more user friendly.*
- *I'm an old user of HADDOCK and after some years of interval I noticed that now the interface is very user friendly and intuitive therefore I'm quite happy.*
- *Considering ligands like metals and sulphates and phosphates are very helpful for this version.*
- *Being able to download the input and parameter files in the portal is easier and the portal is more intuitive.*
- *I really like how inputs are checked at step 1 and the visualization feature for active residues is amazing*
- *The visualization of selected residues for restraints is really helpful*
- *The biggest change I like is that the submission parameters now have explanations of what they do*
- *A lot easier to use*
- *It is just simply PERFECT! Keep it up!*
- *More parameters are available and easily accessible*
- *User friendly interface*
- *Having one interface instead of a range depending on the aims is much simpler*
- *HADDOCK is great*
- *It's easier to navigate around*
- *It is a good server*
- *I like the new add on of glycosylated protein.*
- *My experience with it was amazing. So, I recommend it to everyone who are working in area of structural bioinformatics*
- *I am really happy with this portal ! Thank you !!!*
- *All options are easily accessible and documented. I'm not getting lost*
- *More control can be applied with version 2.4*
- *Visual identification of interface residues helps.*
- *It's great!*
- *I like the feature on selection of active residues, it is very straightforward in version 2.4*
- *Now it is much easier to select the active residues and quite impressive input pattern*
- *The best feature was the prevention of submitting wrong input. Which is really helpful. The design also improved in addition it was nice to see the active residues in a 3d model*
- *This site is fantastic. If a little more popup granular help could be provided it would be fantastic.*
- *The new interface is more user friendly*
- *The 2.4 now can support NAG, I think it's great.*
- *The submission is well-guided, interactive, and straightforward*
- *Everything worked well*

- *For guru level, version 2.4 has more parameters and nice to be used.*
- *This portal is very useful and I always appreciate it.*
- *User friendly*
- *For the evaluation of the results, you can include auxiliary resources related to the interpretation of the data obtained as a result of docking.*
- *The selections available for each level of use are more accessible in the new server format.*
- *The interface is easy*
- *Selection of residues is made easy*
- *This is in no way comparable with the previous one regarding the accessibility of the site, the documentation, and the ease of use.*

Detailed actionable feedback from HADDOCK web server user survey

This section lists suggestions for improvements, which we have categorised and analysed to generate the higher-level aggregated prioritisation described in the main body of this document.

HADDOCK and/or web portal interface functionality:

Input (PDB) preparation, including automation, file format compatibility etc.:

- *Checking the files before submission, visualization of the active and passive residues, etc. It would be cool if the software could automatically know if it is a protein or nucleic acid based on the naming convention, as well as a ligand. Wouldn't it make sense that if the pdb does not have residues or bases named by the standard convention that the software would automatically make it a ligand, even if not name HETATM?*
- *Automatically fix the ion charge error*
- *I have some problem to correct DNA PDB file format. I wish there is a tool to automatically refine pdb files.*
- *Would like old haddockparam files to be reusable in the new version.*
- *Please automate tedious things that must be done for antibody-antigen docking. In particular, extracting CDR residues after the two (H,L) chains have been renumbered to a single chain is something that should be hidden from the user.*
- *The PDB-tools steps that are (required?) for running jobs slowed me down. Again, I think these things can "mostly" be automated.*
- *During the submission of PDB files, various problems were created, it will be great if HADDOCK can automatically solve the problems in PDB file, so that even a novice can use it smoothly.*
- *Improve PDB processing to be more permissive*
- *More flexibility with PDB structures.*
- *Enlarge to other PDB-like files*
- *Some structures in the PDB have multiple versions of the same residue. Enabling the server to handle this scenario would be useful, even if it just*

asked the user to choose which should be used in the analysis.

- *Allow to upload ligand structures in other formats as well (mol, mol2, sdf). Add an interactive interface that shows how organic cofactors are handled, or at least if they pose a problem.*
- *It is very difficult to select the residues for the docking as only 150 can be used in a protein ligand. Also, the server like ClusPro offers docking of two pdb files regardless if they are "prepared" and chains properly numbered. It would be better to simplify ad-hoc docking by allowing submission of less polished PDB files as well as choosing the type of interactions which the HADDOCK should prioritize during the docking (for example vdw for in-membrane domains; electrostatic for peptides in the transporter pore). In the easy accessibility profile, these settings are not visible.*
- *My protein had different residue orientations. After fixing the PDB, I was not able to resubmit the PDB and click "next step" but had to refresh the whole form and fill out everything again. It would be nice if I could just resubmit the fixed PDB. Additionally, my protein has a Zn²⁺ ion, which is documented at the right columns (79-80). However, the web-interface told me, that no charges are specified. Hence, I am currently docking without the Zn²⁺.*
- *For the complexes, portal should allow to upload *.dat file obtained from SAXS data, and in the end it should fit the complex in the envelope. I feel that there should be an option to upload SAXS data (either envelope or *.dat file) for best docking results.*
- *Nucleic material upload format if in FASTA format, should be nice!*
- *Introduce the option to upload protein sequences from a FASTA file.*

Residue / sequence selection:

- *GUI for residues selection*
- *Best practices guide suggests to define the surface of one molecule as passive when we don't know active residues. Sometimes incompatible switches will prevent this selection synced among both molecules. I would then simply add an option to select all residues as active in one partner and passive in the other without dealing with other options.*
- *Sequence selection by mouse clicking could be more reliable by using text based user interface*
- *Ability to choose the active residues from the model directly, by pressing on the residues on the model itself*
- *Add "All" option to specify active residues*
- *Add an interactive graphic interface for choosing the active residues.*
- *Having an option to submit jobs without any active residue? Although it might not be a great idea, I'm not sure.*
- *Do not make declaring active residues for both molecules compulsory. Provide a user friendly interface for the selection of active/passive residues.*
- *Highlighting residues when selecting active site causes previously named*

residues to be cleared, would be nice if that simply added instead of replacing.

- *Visualization of semi-flexible and flexible residues would likely help with submissions.*

Docking parameters and run preparation:

- *The possibility to load/Save custom presets to edit them easily would be useful*
- *Ability to upload complete sets of parameters instead of setting them one by one manually. This can already be saved and it would be useful to also upload such a file.*
- *I hope that we can upload the run.cns to the webserver to perform the docking.*
- *Provide at least one option to change in docking parameters*
- *An access to all docking parameters*
- *Conversion of rigid body to dynamic structure during docking for ligands would be a tremendous help. Also, you could implement the "epitope painting" directly on the surface of the map/PDB file to facilitate selection of prospective binding interface.*
- *Enable advanced parameters*
- *Give access to any user to be able to modify the docking parameters*
- *Some controls of the input parameters would be useful for normal users, like if DNA restraints are necessary (of no DNA is submitted, the user should be able to select no, would help to save resources)*

Overall portal interface usability:

- *Before my account was activated, the input lines were unresponsive. It may be helpful to make it more apparent that the account must be registered*
- *Easier registration*
- *Very lengthy and time consuming registration process*
- *Principal researchers could be able to choose the level of access to the software.*
- *There were a lot of weird greying outs that are hard to differentiate from the light colour of the portal*
- *Better color combination and stability*
- *The new interface is more accessible better shows the various features of HADDOCK, but it could make job submissions easier by being more interactive: if certain input/parameters are detected [e.g. >2 molecules], then incompatible options should be blocked out or highlighted [i.e. solvated docking]. Additionally, restraint file generation could be made more accessible by having a link to the generator webpage in the setup interface.*
- *Remove the separated advanced, expert, and guru options and provide them all outright. Additionally a 'best-practices' page may also be useful.*

- *It would be nice to have a virtual command-line interface*
- *Consider having all the settings in one page*
- *To be able to shift to the expert level directly via the portal*
- *Better visual quality*
- *Editing parameter file would be nice so that less clicking when submitting related jobs*
- *Keeping input parameters/files instead of resetting when an input error is detected or when switching between setup tabs/stages. Perhaps detection of mutually exclusive settings in real time?*

Output and post-processing / analysis of results:

- *More insights to quality control of the docking , whether the docking is a success or not?*
- *I would like the ability to export the metrics from a HADDOCK run as a CSV file. This would help when downloading and combining results.*
- *If RMSD values can be added in the final result.*
- *Often times you need to re-cluster your results because the cutoff is too restrictive or open, it would be awesome if you can have a button on the results page that allows you to input new clustering requirements and have it run on your server. My last run with an FCC of 0.6 resulted in one cluster of 400 structures, therefore I would like the FCC to be more restrictive.*
- *Please make analysis option available near the cluster result so that it is easier to analysis the interaction type and list of amino acids (ligplot 2d view like) also it would be great if you could add effects of mutations thank you*
- *The possibility to download all structures of a cluster at once, it would be nice if I'm able to look at all structures of one cluster at the same time -> clusters of ligands*
- *It would be great if protein-protein interaction interface/residue diagrams are provided*
- *It would be convenient if we could look back the active residues used in the results directly as well*
- *Clearer analysis of haddock score n z score*
- *pdb file converter for ARIA output files*
- *The server could present double extra plots and information about docking. Actually, the current concept is quite well. I just recommend the server to give extra plot or graph or map or network information*
- *I noticed that it would be useful to visualise protein and ligand separately (if you inspect your docking poses) otherwise it might be hard to see your ligand.*
- *Provide the result as a 3d model*

Performance, resources, job execution and management:

- *Results can be given faster*
- *Faster process please*
- *Quick runtime to get the results*
- *More speed*
- *Job take too much time to get completed*
- *It would be very helpful if docking results can be obtained within 1-2 hours at the very least*
- *Reduction of calculation time*
- *Kindly I would like to see jobs being processed within short time possible.*
- *User should be able to look the progress (in detail) when running jobs. Also, user may want to cancel the job even after submission.*
- *You could put the link to the workspace when the job is ready, I got confused in the job's page.*
- *Write the number of queued jobs so I have an idea how long I have to wait*
- *Please don't restrict much on the job names since an error of it will require us to upload every file again.*
- *Minor inconvenience: Invalid job name titles should be marked as invalid before the user hits the 'Next' button so as to not require the user to re-upload pdb structures. Or, a live character counter could be displayed next to the job title input field.*
- *I would like to see a log window that details the user actions and possible problems generated. It could be as user request.*
- *Abort button is needed, to abort a run after submission if necessary.*
- *An indicator/estimator of how docking parameters could affect docking time would be sweet*
- *Scoring method and time to complete*
- *The only detail I miss is the function to follow the detailed run progress.*
- *It will be helpful to get estimate on completion time for each job.*
- *It would be great to be able to save parameter between runs*
- *When making a mistake with the pub format- make it easier to resubmit the job with the corrected pub file*
- *Make simpler to save the input parameters for reporting in publications*
- *Include a link to job history on the profile of a user account. It would help like a million times*
- *Include a history of job submissions on the profile and then a dummy submission set up that shows how different choices change outcomes.*
- *Send results to user's email may be better*
- *If it is possible, I would like to get a clear notification when the job submitted is received*

Other:

- *Active site prediction*

- *Add data on binding energy to compare the various complexes*
- *Due to the number of tunable parameters it seems that in the absence of information regarding PPI the result of the docking could be very poor and unreliable.*
- *It would be very helpful to increase the number for active residues in the docking, especially for large proteins, with a lot of solvent accessible surface areas. Additionally, it would be also very helpful to have a tool to calculate solvent accessible surface areas and if the web server could generate files for MD simulations with gromacs at the end of the docking run.*
- *I really like the possibility to use glycans in the docking. However, since glycans can be used in the docking runs now, it would be very helpful, if there is also a possibility for glycoproteins beside just using the normal protein docking run with glycans as heteroatoms.*
- *I would love to have an docking options for glycoproteins and membrane (glyco-)proteins*
- *Small issues like having glycans, heteroatoms, etc make it impossible to submit the job, and thus create unreliable results -- because I have to delete important parts of my structure.*
- *Please allow HADDOCK to read overlapping residue identifiers, it's very difficult to change them when using big molecules.*
- *A feature for RNA DNA structural refinement and modelling*
- *Sometimes it's hard to predict interface of the query protein, so it will be great if the whole protein residues are subjected to modelling (docking)*
- *Allowing residues from different chains to have the same residue*
- *Add possibility to define explicitly flexible residues in receptor.*
- *Active and passive residue restriction should be avoided.*
- *Improve the software adding the possibility to use modified peptides*
- *Extend to allow for 'blind' docking. That is, when you do NOT have experimental restraints to feed in*
- *There can be an option for the users to define if they need active residues and passive residues. Some dockings are usually considered for blind docking. Just a suggestion*
- *Create tools for blind docking. I'd like to do blind docking, my ligand is new and i don't know where exactly binds to the protein of interest*
- *The identification of active residues takes time, I wish we had an easier way to do so blindly without specifying active residues...i.e. blind docking*
- *I don't know much with the use of active site input option but I believe its not user friendly. I am docking two proteins whose interactions are not known at all and in that case how come I define the active residues. Logically I want to do blind docking and want to study the poses based on my domain and other features understanding. The active site residues page was the biggest hinder in my docking study and finally I had to submit my job by selecting the highest number of allowed residues in the column, which*

- is 150aa. hence the interface should be simple and should be in user control.*
- *I would hope it would work without an a priori knowledge of active/passive residues.*
 - *A global docking option without restraints or active sites being specified is expected.*
 - *Please add the active site prediction tool into HADDOCK. The other servers are very time consuming option when applied*
 - *Can HADDOCK and CPORT can be integrated into one service? For calculating active residue, I'm using CPORT for HADDOCK input. If CPORT and HADDOCK can be merged into one, then it will be more easier to use service*
 - *CPORT can be made a part of HADDOCK*
 - *Add an option to allow user to directly interface CPort for active residues prediction*
 - *Can you improve the ARIA calculation*
 - *It would be great if we could define NOEs between proteins and select ligand atoms. If this is already possible please share a corresponding tutorial.*
 - *Capability of dock multiple protein may be (3 or 4) to same receptor site.*
 - *Additional results on Protein-Ligand/peptide interacting aminoacid residues and their bond length would be appreciable. Thanks*
 - *About PPI interaction, could be useful to predict IC50 on docked cluster results.*
 - *Docking should contain specified residues. I am docking two proteins. I know the interacting site of one but not the other one, so you must keep that in option too. In literature only one interacting site is specified and not the other one, so the web server should consider that.*
 - *Parameters for more post-translational modification for amino acids*
 - *There is a residue that is not on the surface, and the experiment indicates to participate of the interaction. However, I could not select this residue because was not on the surface. I think that the portal just let performing the calculation with a warning.*
 - *There is a limit of 150 (max.) for active residues for docking, that would be problematic because in my case, more than 150 active residues are predicted. Please update to maximum limit up to 1000.*
 - *Implementation of machine learning or deep learning based algorithms*
 - *The process to submit multi ligand peptide against one protein is tedious*
 - *It would be great to also be able to edit/change topology and/or parameter files in toppar*
 - *Hints and GUI (a more slick image would be cool)*
 - *Enhance multi peptide screening.*
 - *Make sure that mutually exclusive options behave properly such as RAIRs and AIRs/UAIRs*

- *Maybe a way to create .tbl files using a form input rather than figuring out the syntax on our own.*
- *To provide user with Protein-Peptide direct form*
- *Check of nomenclature (atom naming, residue correspondence) ambig.tbl /unambig.tbl before running, for instance by doing the NOE-SEL and checking whether 0 atoms were atoms were selected*
- *Some suggestions:*
 - *Input peptide as primary sequence with no structural information*
 - *Designate simple structural tendencies (-1 to 1 for extended to helical structure)*
 - *Designate simple residue-residue contacts between interaction partners (id1 resn1 id2 resn2)*
- *Could be useful to allow interpretation of subunits with multiple chains, rather than having to renumber residues. Would facilitate symmetry restraints.*
- *The molecules should be prepared automatically on the web server.*
- *Support more formats for different atoms produce by AMBER, GROMACS or CHARMM*
- *Provide a link to make an ensemble or make it directly*
- *I would love to be able to set specific restraints (i.e. 121 in A to 255 in B and 141 in A to 291 in B) rather than just general restraints (i.e. 121,141 to 255,291) using the "easy" mode. It seems expert access is required for these relatively straightforward restraint specifications..*
- *A bit more customization in easy mode with specific residue-residue restraints between two models would be very useful.*
- *Ligand binding can take place at locations between subunits of membrane proteins so an improvement would be to allow for designation of multiple chains and selection of identical residues between them.*
- *Tried coarse graining my models, CG was incompatible with some water model which could not be changed in "easy mode", thus the coarse grain option is in practise not available in easy mode.*
- *gRPC API*
- *The format supported for nucleic acid should be more easy to archive*
- *Need support for new type of proteins.*
- *The ability to incorporate a wider variety of amino acid modifications would be very useful*

Detailed feedback regarding assistance in interface, documentation, tutorials etc.

- *More detail for each option (I like detail)*
- *Include scroll-over pop-up examples of inputs. For instance, during declaration of active residues it was not immediately clear it was necessary only to use residue index and not include letter symbols. Utilizing a quick*

text example of input forms or visualization throughout at each section (that requires a nuanced entry) will be extremely useful for ease of use.

- *More clear way to start running the docking*
- *Add a quick reference help popup about how to define residues in selections. is it A/34-72, 34:72, resid 34-72, a.34:72, etc? Every program uses a different syntax, and there is no clue shown about what haddock uses! [Eventually I found it buried deep in a random, unrelated example...]*
- *Easier explanation for non experts*
- *Examples in each step*
- *Should specify the advanced parameters that are important for interaction studies. Some of the constraints are not clear. This must be explained as a flow chart at the user interface.*
- *Please present an easy flow chart for the analysis of docked results and their visualization showing interaction such as h bonds*
- *More information on how to prepare the structures. It took some time for me to figure out how to prepare my antibody structures as they have two chains.*
- *Maybe we could move our mouse to a term or a sentence of instructions and have a detailed display of what it means*
- *In the submission portal, maybe the different options can be linked to their corresponding sections in the manual. That way, it would be easier for users look at the details a specific option.*
- *Add tutorial in each step*
- *Tutorial videos for dummies*
- *Add tutorial video for user and help to understand the different parameters and output analysis through an example.*
- *A shortcut to a tutorial might be useful*
- *Not sure where to find interacting active residues. This needs some help docs.*
- *Documentation on tbl file syntax*
- *I am a new user and take time to submit active residue please provide example of residue and its format. I tried many time and take two days after removing comma from last active residue then I successfully submit my job. so please provide information these small information although tutorials are available but these small points are missing.*
- *More links to tutorials FAQs. Instructions on how to prepare the PDB files*
- *Some tutorial exercises on protein-protein docking with all options, including advanced options, to understand their applicability will be really helpful. Sometimes we might have data or additional restraints from other experiments which we would not otherwise apply when using HADDOCK since we are not clear about the advanced docking options. Such a tutorial encompassing all options will be really useful.*
- *HADDOCK2.4 refinement interface may need to be more self-explaining. I*

had ions in my complex. It took me a few tests to realize that the ion and protein should be in the same chain, so that the server could identify it as a "Protein-ion" entity. Refinement interface could use more guidelines, explanations embedded within the page or a direct link to one of the available documents, maybe.

- *It would be nice to know the reliability of HADDOCK on small molecules and their parametrization.*
- *Comments or instructions or just small guides*
- *A bigger FAQ section*
- *Provide update research paper with elaborated methodology and results*
- *Step by step performing CPORT for protein and hopefully for nucleic acid as well*
- *Please show more figure to guide process*
- *When I suggest active residues on the first protein, it complains that I have to specify them on both sides and does not hint that I can make second one passive*
- *Parameters are not easy to understand.*
- *Tutorials should be easier to find maybe*
- *May be make the web tool package more accessible. I spent hours download pdbtools and struggling with them.*
- *Describe how to find active residues of protein which do not have 4 unit pdb id*
- *Help pointer with additional notes/links to each of the available options.*
- *The access privileges are a little confusing, it's not clear (for me) what I need to do to have the ability to modify the default parameters.*
- *A better manual/tutorial on how to use the standalone/offline Haddock 2.4*
- *Maybe a little summary of what each parameter does*
- *Better clarity in the tutorials will be appreciated*
- *Not quite understandable to choose the parameters before submission*
- *The Antibody-Antigen Tutorial can't be followed as it is due to not being able to change advanced settings.*
- *Please provide more tutorials for us.*
- *Making the web portal with links to expected inputs*
- *It is good overall and my small suggestion is please give hint at each options like NOTE at active site residues selection like maximum residues limit like that information*
- *I would add a hyperlink to a working file for ligands, proteins and so on. This would maybe easier for beginners to figure out the correct input format. This might prevent frequent questions in the forum*
- *Helpful to know if I shouldn't be using Chrome browser*
- *How to determine the active residues of the predicted protein structure by AlphaFold2? Is it possible to submit without entering active residues*
- *It would be appreciable if clear directions are mentioned as to how to*

modify the PDB files to upload and the format of each parameter.

- *More mouse-over explanations of all options*
- *It was not clear how to proceed when we want to start with an ensemble of structures instead of a single model*
- *Suggest what form input should be in*
- *Hover icons over particular definitions and parameters, preferably to hyperlinks with documentation/best practice guide especially for docking restraints*
- *Video explanation of how to understand the results*
- *More assistance while putting the options parameters.*
- *Some explanations mainly focus on the local software while some focus on the webserver, so you have to switch and see where to change the parameters. A unified tutorial would therefore be cool*
- *A little explanation of the parameters details for new users and new students at molecular modelling studies*
- *Tutorial for PDB Preparation*
- *Maybe add a small description for each parameter? Honestly I think it's good enough.*
- *The options feel daunting as a new user, and things like identifying active sites before submitting feels completely foreign. Better descriptions of resources or tools to point new users towards identifying features would make it feel easier and more friendly.*
- *Some tutorial videos for Protein-DNA docking would be really helpful for beginners.*
- *I always think it's nice if each parameter displays an example input, this serves as a quick guide or tutorial (would be useful to immediately know the formatting for active/passive residues, could also be useful for understanding other input file formats)*
- *If you could help us in analysis of results through a video it would be very useful.*
- *I would like a little video tutorial on how choose residues implicated in the interaction when we have no informations about it*
- *Would you please improve and detail more about analysis of results and how to report it in articles?*
- *Chain IDs reading is often difficult*
- *Some quick links under each selection/function tab to quickly describe to the user what is being asked to fill in.*
- *It was really good. Please give more convenient details about coarse grain docking with the use of gromacs.*
- *Better define what some of the parameter options are/do*
- *Provide description of each parameter along side for new users*
- *Explain better how to create PDB for ligands in the HETATM format*
- *Suggestions how to edit PDB files maybe*

- *More detailed description of each parameter and what they do.*
- *In order to attract a major number of users we could have a very beginners guide*
- *More video tutorials*
- *Please separate the it0, it1 and itw. so give any hint to differentiate these parameters*
- *Please give more information about flexible docking*
- *More description of how to select input PDB type*
- *For people who first time use the server, it is not very easy to go through all the steps, maybe provide an overall workflow could be better.*
- *Quick statements about the parameter when the cursor is on the top of the parameter*
- *A thorough manual or video with stepwise description is required to submit properly*
- *The new web portal is easier to navigate but it would be nice to have more descriptions of the input options directly on the page*
- *The system did not accept my protein, which contained an iron atom, because the charge was missing. I changed the input data manually, but nothing helped despite deleting the heteroatoms. It might be nice to redirect to a page/manual, that explains, how to correctly label the charged atoms. Nevertheless, thanks for the great tool ;-)*
- *Kindly mention hints for each input parameters.*
- *I would like to see Pop up with tips & hints for every parameter to be set up*
- *If there is more explanation on how each parameter may affect the result, that would be helpful for new users.*
- *I didn't see any "manual tab" on HADDOCK2.4 on the webpage. I am amazed how many parameters HADDOCK2.4 allows users to adjust but would learn more how they affect the results.*
- *Slightly hard to tell which options were available as an EASY user vs ADVANCED. I know they were shaded, but I couldn't quite tell on the last page prior to submission (with all the detailed parameters to tune)*
- *Link for tutorial on how to use the portal for the newcomers*
- *More instructions for the buttons used*
- *State example of active residue comma delineated: 1,2,3,4. (vs. V1, A2, T3)*
- *I wish it can be easier to find all relevant page*
- *An easy interactive input for NOEs both for protein-protein and protein-ligand docking runs.*
- *Better tutorial on how to add charge to ion/ how to make sure the model is acceptable*
- *Providing sample input as example for every step can make it more easier*
- *Make full guide for user*
- *Explain the different options for specific problems*
- *Description of the tools to change your PDB in order to make it compatible*

with the software (great interface to even change them online - but I am not certain what all these commands can be used for) other than that amazingly user friendly - took me only one day to read through it

- *The documentation for some of the "Easy" parameters, i.e. what exactly do "active" and "passive" residues imply could be either linked or explained via a little infobox (like in Charmm-GUI)*
- *More descriptive side documentation*
- *A button could be added to load an example that allows testing the server with known data for new users.*
- *More help on items that user must set, now it requires high knowledge*
- *Please provide an example of the input format for interacting residues below the submission row. eg 56, 87, 105*
- *I think it should be more user friendly with more expansion especially about the parameters.*
- *Having links to explanations of parameters to choose when submitting a job would help*
- *Please add visuals of steps in user guide*
- *User friendly guide to understand results*
- *A video tutorial would be helpful*
- *HADDOCK is great --- but you need more documentation on how to properly annotate charged heteroatoms. Also any glycosylated protein can't be submitted :-{(*
- *The tutorials are based on the web server. A specific section about how to use the different tools of HADDOCK locally could be helpful (with the same detail as for the web server)*
- *Show examples of how to correctly format PDBs containing ions*
- *Short description of selection features as "hints" next to the selection will further make it easier to use.*
- *More description in pop-up help tabs*
- *It would really help if examples were provided at each step (utilising a pop up after clicking a (?) question mark with the brief explanation). This would make things much easier to understand such as the usual format for PDB files (for ligand) or how to select residues.*
- *A detailed tutorial about output analysis*
- *Short help pop ups*
- *Help button beside some of the options*
- *Example files or demonstration for submission should be added.*
- *More elaborate documentation needed.*
- *You could describe better the scores used to classify the clusters and the models.*
- *More descriptive tooltips*
- *Predefined docking examples*
- *I found it difficult to validate pdb file of protein. Did not find guidelines self*

explanatory

- *It would be better if providing a protocol for loading input*
- *It will be useful to point out some important parameters (besides active residues) to be modified/tried in the notes, while other parameters remained default.*
- *Quick popups with reference examples or usage case*
- *The restriction of specifying docking parameters to higher access levels seems pointless. Perhaps either clarify why that restriction is in place or remove it.*
- *Make the Haddock 2.4 library more accessible, perhaps link it to relevant errors. It is on the Haddock main page, but only if you know to scroll*
- *Showing some explanation (link or tags) for the different restrain parameters or what is what or what is meant if we select that option will be great help*
- *Put example for every input type beside.*
- *Having small info boxes next to each thing to help with the understanding. I tried submitting the job 4 times before I realized that I had to remove the single letter code from the sequence in order to proceed.*

Detailed feedback regarding errors, error messages and error handling

- *When getting an error message, would be nice to provide more explanations about why the error occurred and how to fix it. Sometimes the information provided isn't enough to help me completely understand why it failed.*
- *More clear errors with input structures or a tutorial of how they should look would be useful*
- *Maybe one could have an example how to fix errors. Like the error "First pdb file contains multiple chains with overlapping numbering: A4 - B4" could be illustrated with an example nicely.*
- *Errors explanation may help*
- *Granular feedback help identifying what specific parameters prevented job submission.*
- *I had initial problems submitting the job. I found out by trial and error it was probably due to selecting too many active residues, but the message that came up when I tried to submit seemed like a warning, rather than something which would prevent the job from starting.*
- *I often had problems with the server's processing of the input files. If you could either make it less strict or at least provide more detailed error messages, it would be great.*
- *Job submission was not accepted for unknown reasons multiple times*
- *Moving from tab could leads into delay, if something go wrong you have to restart from the beginning and is difficult do do a final check of all the parameters before running the job*

- *When you do not supply active residues it says you need to supply them for the first model. Then if you supply them for the first model it says you need to supply them for both models.*
- *Every error removes the previously loaded data*
- *Update so that the user does not have to restart the process each time something gets flagged*
- *When in the first step one uploaded .pdb file is incorrect, all the uploaded .pdb files have to be uploaded again, it would be convenient when only the 'wrong' .pdf needs to be uploaded again. Furthermore, the link towards 'powerfit' at the centroids restraints tab of step2 does not work*
- *More descriptive error messages and brief suggestions for possible ways to fix them.*
- *More specific error messages*
- *Some errors have been addressed in Q&A, I suggest providing a link in the error message.*
- *User-prepared input files easily contain errors. If you can print a correct format along with the error message, it will be very helpful.*
- *More explicit suggestions for errors*
- *Give some extra help on how to fix pdb file issues in error message or maybe at least provide links to discussion pages*
- *A more detailed error report for parsing errors.*
- *Post-completion error must be avoided if possible*
- *Gives error if the residues has similar names. In ligand there is no showing the chain ID. So please add chain ID with sequences.*
- *I would like to get a feed-back whether my explicite, unambiguous restraints could be read or not. I did not find much information on the format to use for pseudoatoms in methyl groups or aromatic rings. If I knew immediately that the format is not correct, I would gain time not waiting for the run to complete*

Detailed feedback regarding potential bugs

- *The structure preview didn't match the uploaded structure*
- *fix error of cannot sparse () spaces, add info about how to add charge to atoms. could not figure it out and deleted them.*
- *Currently, when I start multiple runs, the models uploaded for the first run appear when I click "visualize residues" when starting subsequent runs with different input models. Actives do not display in the "visualize residues" window when this happens, but no error is returned saying the residues are not in the model and the run goes as expected. Overall, not a big deal, but I figured I'd mention it. I am using Firefox in Linux Mint.*
- *Some of my colleagues reported metal ions in the PDBs not working properly on the 2.4, if you could kindly look into that.*

- *The submission of saved parameter does not seem to work.*
- *Sometimes the web server hangs and I am unable to submit a job*
- *I input an active residue that should have been exposed but it was not registered as such*
- *I just have an issue with the part where you visualize the active residues; I submitted three jobs, and it remembered the structure of the first molecule I submitted (there were three variants). At this point, I do not know if this is just a display problem, or if it will also ignore the variations while performing docking. Otherwise, the interface is really nice and friendly.*
- *The list of active residues which I provided is not in the results*
- *It doesn't seem to work in Safari; I had to use Firefox.*
- *I noticed there is a potential bug: if I try to visualize the active residues that I have selected for my Molecule 2 (which I defined as "Peptide"), Molecule 1 (the protein/receptor) is shown instead. Shouldn't I see Molecule 2 on the screen?*
- *It would be nice if I can view the model analysis plot. I am not sure why I can't. And the plots I downloaded are all blank images.*

Appendix 2: AstraZeneca virtual training flyer

Virtual training on Molecular Dynamics and advanced free energy calculations using GROMACS/PMX and workflows using BioExcel building blocks.

Dates: Tuesday 13th (session 1) and Friday 23rd (session 2) October 2020

Time: 07:00 - 12:00 EST / 12:00 - 17:00 GMT / 13:00 - 18:00 CET

Duration: each session will last up to 5 hours, depending on the level of interactivity.

Location: <https://embl-de.zoom.us/j/91428037712> (Password: 889712).

Session 1 – Molecular Dynamics and advanced free energy calculations

Overview

- Lecture on free energy background, with a focus on non-equilibrium alchemical free energy calculations.
- Lecture on PMX applications: protein stability, DNA-protein binding, relative and absolute ligand affinities.
- Hands-on tutorial on usage of PMX/GROMACS on ligand affinity estimates

Learning outcomes

At the end of this session you will have:

- An overview of free energy calculation methods.
- An insight into non-equilibrium alchemical free energies.
- An overview of the state-of-the-art of mutation free energies.
- Hands-on experience with calculating relative ligand affinities with PMX/GROMACS.

Target audience

This session is aimed at people with an interest in free energy calculations, ideally with expertise in Molecular Dynamics, GROMACS and Linux.

Installation requirements

For everything to run smoothly during the session we need you to have pre-installed the following tools. Please complete the installations BEFORE Monday 12th October.

- **Python 3** with **NumPy** (<https://numpy.org/install/>) and **matplotlib** (<https://matplotlib.org/users/installing.html>).
- **PMX** "develop" branch (<https://github.com/deGrootLab/pmx>): required version will be available for download in October 2020.
- **RDkit** version 2018.09.1 (<https://github.com/rdkit/rdkit/releases>)
- **Pymol**

If you have any questions regarding the installations for session 1 please do not hesitate to contact Vytas Gapsys (vgapsys@gwdg.de) or Bert de Groot (bgroot@gwdg.de).

BioExcel is funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 program under grant agreements 823830 and 675728.

Session 2 – Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks

Overview

- Introductory lecture to BioExcel building blocks.
- Hands-on tutorial on setting up protein and protein-complex Molecular Dynamics with GROMACS using BioExcel building blocks.
- Hands-on tutorial on setting up protein mutation free energy calculations with GROMACS/PMX using BioExcel building blocks.

Learning outcomes

At the end of this session you will be able to:

- Interactively work with computational biomolecular simulation demonstration workflows built using the BioExcel building blocks library in Jupyter Notebooks sessions: change input structure, modify parameters, add/remove steps, etc.
- Write a new computational biomolecular simulation workflow using the BioExcel building blocks library from scratch.
- Launch computational biomolecular simulation workflows built using the BioExcel building blocks library in a command-line interface.

Target audience

This session is aimed at people interested in:

- Starting with computational biomolecular simulations, and more specifically Molecular Dynamics simulations and free energy calculations using GROMACS/PMX.
- Building computational biomolecular simulations workflows, ensuring reproducibility.

Installation requirements

For everything to run smoothly during the session we need you to install **Anaconda** and **Docker** tools, download the three **tutorials** and configure **Conda** environments for them. We have prepared step-by-step instructions for you to follow and this should only take around 10 minutes. Please complete the installations BEFORE Thursday 22nd October. If you have any issues please do not hesitate to contact us:

1) Install **Anaconda package manager** (Linux / MacOS), Python 3.7
<https://docs.anaconda.com/anaconda/install/>

2) Install **Docker Desktop** (MacOS, Windows) / **Docker Linux Engine** (Linux)
<https://www.docker.com/products/docker-desktop>

3) Download all three **Tutorial Workflows** and configure **Conda Environments** for them
(<http://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/tutorials>):

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Workflow 1: Protein MD Setup

http://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/tutorials/md_setup

```
1) Clone workflow from git repository
git clone https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb\_wf\_md\_setup.git
cd biobb_wf_md_setup

2) Create Conda environment with dependencies
conda env create -f conda_env/environment.yml

3) Activate Conda environment
conda activate biobb_MDsetup_tutorial

4) Activate Jupyter Notebook extensions for NGLView molecular viewer
jupyter-nbextension enable --py --user widgetsnbextension
jupyter-nbextension enable --py --user ngiview

5) Launch Jupyter Notebook tutorial
jupyter-notebook biobb_wf_md_setup/notebooks/biobb_MDsetup_tutorial.ipynb
```

Workflow 2: Protein-Complex MD Setup

http://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/tutorials/protein-complex_md_setup

```
1) Clone workflow from git repository
git clone https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb\_wf\_protein-complex\_md\_setup.git
cd biobb_wf_protein-complex_md_setup

2) Create Conda environment with dependencies
conda env create -f conda_env/environment.yml

3) Activate Conda environment
conda activate biobb_Protein-Complex_MDsetup_tutorial

4) Activate Jupyter Notebook extensions for NGLView molecular viewer
jupyter-nbextension enable --py --user widgetsnbextension
jupyter-nbextension enable --py --user ngiview

5) Launch Jupyter Notebook tutorial
jupyter-notebook biobb_wf_protein-complex_md_setup/notebooks/biobb_Protein-Complex_MDsetup_tutorial.ipynb
```

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Workflow 3: Mutation Free Energy Calculations

<http://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/tutorials/pmx>

```
1) Clone workflow from git repository
git clone https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb\_wf\_pmx\_tutorial.git
cd biobb_wf_pmx_tutorial

2) Create Conda environment with dependencies
conda env create -f conda_env/environment.yml

3) Activate Conda environment
conda activate biobb_wf_pmx_tutorial

4) Activate Jupyter Notebook extension for Plotly graphing library
jupyter-nbextension enable --py --user widgetsnbextension

5) Launch Jupyter Notebook tutorial
jupyter-notebook biobb_wf_pmx_tutorial/notebooks/biobb_wf_pmx_tutorial.ipynb
```

If you have any questions regarding the installations for session 2 please do not hesitate to contact Adam Hospital (adam.hospital@irbbarcelona.org) or Pau Andrio (pau.andrio@bsc.es).

Appendix 3: KOL interviews full list of questions

PART 0 – About you

- Briefly describe your background
- What is your domain of expertise?
- What activities do you carry out within this domain?
- Do you use HPC, and if not, why not?
- What is your/your team's current usage of computing infrastructure, and do you face any bottlenecks in terms of available resources?

PART 1 – Reaching Exascale: areas of life science where exascale computing will be important/essential

- Pushing computational capabilities towards Exascale is part of the mission of the BioExcel CoE. Which are the biggest challenges in reaching Exascale Computing in the Life Sciences?
- Which advances in computing are going to have the biggest impact in reaching Exascale?
- BioExcel is focused on Biomolecular Modelling and Simulation. What does BioExcel need to capitalise on these advances?
 - Does BioExcel have this now?
 - What is holding BioExcel back?
 - Is specific expertise required?
 - How important is co-design?
 - Are there additional partners we should engage?
- How could BioExcel implement, test and showcase these advances?
 - Which existing BioExcel-supported codes would play a part?
 - Are additional capabilities (*Structure Modelling, Bioinformatics, Cheminformatics*) required for this?
 - Can you think of specific 'impact' use cases? (*by impact we mean at the societal level, rather than scientific domain level*)
 - Can you think of any use cases?
- Increased computation capability and usability will result in increased data generation. How can BioExcel ensure that BioExcel-generated data provides value beyond its current use?
 - Which data should BioExcel focus on preserving?
 - What are the future needs for this data?
 - How should BioExcel make this data available to the broader community?
 - Do you think FAIR principles are important?

PART 2 – User-driven development: use cases and grand challenges of scientific and industrial importance in the context of current user and future user

- Based on existing capabilities which societal/scientific challenges could BioExcel address?

- Would this change if BioExcel were to bring in additional capabilities?
- How would it change?
- Which additional capabilities?
- Which use cases or pilot studies would best demonstrate how these challenges are addressed?
 - Which partners or existing initiatives should BioExcel engage with?

PART 3 – User engagement and support: provision of end-to-end support for our users

- Do you participate in BioExcel user engagement (forums, surveys, webinars)
 - Are you aware of these user engagement platforms?
 - What do you like best?
 - What could be better?
- Are you aware of the training which is available through BioExcel?
 - Have you participated in any of this training?
 - Which?
 - Are there particular areas or modes of training that you think BioExcel should cover in the future?
- Given unlimited time/effort and no EC regulations, where/how do you think BioExcel should expand the training programme to maximise its impact?
- Would you like to ‘build your own’ training?
 - Would you pay for premium, bespoke training?
 - What could this premium training look like?
- A not-for-profit members organisation (BXL-E) will be established to build on the principles and achievements of the BioExcel Centre of Excellence (CoE) and will continue to operate beyond the CoE project lifetime. Our **vision** is that BXL-E will focus its operational activities on; (i) **provision of infrastructure** which supports members’ core activities and facilitates engagement with external communities, and (ii) **delivering services** which foster collaboration and increase the quality of scientific research in the field.
 - Can you see your organisation (or yourself) being a member of BXL-E?
 - If yes, would it be feasible for you/your organisation to pay a membership fee?
 - What kind of infrastructure could BXL-E provide?
 - What kind of services could BXL-E provide?

PART 4 – Additional questions

- Are there any important topics which we did not cover today?
- Are there additional questions we should ask external KOLs?
- Are there any questions we should rephrase and how?

- Can you suggest specific KOLs we should interview?